

Extracting Connectivity of
Bidirectional Networks from Dynamics
從動力學提取雙向網絡的連通性

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The study of networks has become increasingly important in many disciplines ranging from physics to biology. A network consists of many elementary components which interact with one another. The elementary components are known as the nodes while the interactions among the nodes are the links or connections of the network. In order to understand the function and properties of a network, a crucial first step is to determine how the nodes are linked or connected to each other. It is often difficult to directly measure or observe the connectivity between nodes. Thus a method that infers the connectivity of an unknown network from measurements would be highly valuable. Many methods have been proposed to address this difficult inverse problem of network reconstruction. One approach is to model networks by dynamical systems with the time evolution of the nodes given by ordinary differential equations. We have recently developed a method that reconstructs the connectivity of a network using only the measured time series of the nodes. Earlier studies required additional information such as the coupling strength

or the response of the network to external perturbations, which are difficult to obtain in realistic situations. Our method is based on a noise-induced relation between the network connectivity and the dynamical covariance of the nodes, and is applicable for networks in which the coupling between nodes is bidirectional. In realistic networks, the strength of interaction among nodes often varies from node to node but most network reconstruction studies focus on the simpler case of uniform coupling strength. For weighted networks with non-uniform coupling strength, it is especially hard to predict the relative strength or weight of the links. Our method can also infer the normalized coupling strength of the links for weighted networks. In this thesis, we shall present our method and demonstrate that it gives satisfactory reconstruction of the connectivity and the normalized coupling strength for different types of networks with both linear and nonlinear dynamics.

概要

有關網絡的研究對從物理學到生物學等許多學科都越來越重要。一個網絡是由許多相互作用的基本部分所組成。這些基本部分被稱為節點，而節點之間的相互作用則為該網絡的連結。要理解網絡的功能以及性質，關鍵的第一步是要確定節點如何互相連接。這種節點之間的連結往往是難以直接測量或觀察到的，因此如果能從測量到的數據去推斷未知網絡的連通性，將會是非常有價值的。已經有人提出許多方法來解決網絡重建這個棘手的逆問題。其中一種方法是通過動力學模型來描述網絡，並以常微分方程給出節點隨著時間的演化。我們最近開發了一種只需要節點的時間序列就能重建網絡的方法。在此之前的研究往往需要其他信息去重建網絡，例如連結的強度或網絡對外部擾動的反應，但這都是很難在實際情況下獲得的。我們的方法是基於網絡的連通性和節點的動態共變異數之間由雜訊引起的關係，並且適用於雙向網絡。在現實的網絡中，節點之間相互作用的強度往往各不相同，但大多數網絡重建研究均集中處理均勻的連結強度的簡單情況。對於擁有非均勻連結強度的加權網絡，它的連結的相對強度是特別難以預測的。我們的方法可以推斷出加權網絡連結的標準化強度。在本論文中，我們將介紹這個網絡重建的方法，並以不同類型的網絡，以及線性和非線性的動力學模型來示範它能夠準確地推斷網絡的連通性和連結的標準化強度。

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Contents

Abstract	i
Acknowledgements	iv
1 Introduction	1
1.1 An overview of the study of networks	1
1.2 The problem of network inference	5
2 Review of Existing Methods of Network Reconstruction	8
2.1 Statistical correlation and information-theoretic measures	9
2.2 Bayesian network	13
2.3 Inverse Ising inference	16
2.4 Dynamical systems approach	19
3 A Novel Method of Network Reconstruction	24
3.1 The theory	25
3.2 Method for Reconstruction of Connectivity	32
3.2.1 Algorithm for unweighted networks	33
3.2.2 Algorithm for weighted networks	35
3.3 Method for Reconstruction of Normalized Coupling Strength and Node Strength	36
3.4 Evaluating the method	36

3.4.1	Simulating the unweighted networks	39
3.4.2	Simulating the weighted networks	42
4	Reconstruction of Network Connectivity: Sensitivity and Specificity	45
4.1	Results for unweighted networks	47
4.2	Results for weighted networks	62
5	Reconstruction of Normalized Coupling Strength and Node Strength	74
6	Reconstruction of Global Network Properties: Eigenvalue Spectrum, Degree and Strength Distribution	87
6.1	Results for unweighted networks	88
6.2	Results for weighted networks	93
7	Conclusion and Outlook	101
7.1	Summary	101
7.2	Limitations of our method and suggestions for further investigation	103
A	Numerical Methods used in Solving Stochastic Differential Equations (SDE)	108
A.1	The Euler-Maruyama method	108
A.2	The Weak Order 2 Runge-Kutta (RKW2) method	109
	Bibliography	111

List of Figures

1.1	A network consisting of 6 nodes	2
2.1	Network structure with (a) a direct and high-order connection between nodes u and v , and (b) only an indirect connection between nodes u and v . Figure taken from Ref. [49].	10
4.1	The values of $r_i(m)$ as a function of m for a certain node i of the random network with consensus dynamics and $\sigma = g = 1$	48
4.2	$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for random network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\sigma = g = 1$), (b) FHN1 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$), and (c) FHN2 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$).	51
4.3	$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for random network with the cubic coupling form $h(x_i, x_j) = (x_j - x_i)^3$ ($\sigma = g = 1$).	51
4.4	$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for random network with consensus dynamics using $\sigma = g = 1$ without the requirement of $m_0(i) \neq 1$	52
4.5	$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for random network with the Kuramoto model using $\sigma = g = 1$. We label the particularly low $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ of the node $i = 8$ with a closed circle.	52

4.6	The values of ω_i used in the simulation, which is drawn from a Lorentz distribution. The node $i = 8$ which has a very low $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ is labeled with a closed circle.	53
4.7	The time series $\theta_i(t)$ of the Kuramoto model on the random network for the node $i = 8$ (black) and three other nodes with more typical ω_i (red, blue and green).	53
4.8	Same as Fig. 4.5 but with a larger coupling strength $g = 10$. Note that $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ of the node $i = 8$ (closed circle) shows marked improvement over the case with smaller $g = 1$	54
4.9	Same as Fig. 4.7 but with a larger coupling strength $g = 10$	54
4.10	Same as Fig. 4.2 for the C. Elegans neuronal network.	55
4.11	Same as Fig. 4.2 for the BA scale-free network.	56
4.12	$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for BA scale-free network with FHN2 dynamics using $\sigma = g = 1$ without the requirement of $m_0(i) \neq 1$	57
4.13	The measure of quality of separation $\delta(i)$ for node i against node degree k_i on the BA scale-free network with FHN1 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$). The red solid line is proportional to $1/k_i$ and is for guiding the eye.	58
4.14	Same as Fig. 4.13 but for FHN2 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$) on BA scale-free network. The red solid line is proportional to $1/k_i$ and is for guiding the eye.	58
4.15	The number of false negatives n_{fn} for node i against node degree k_i on the BA scale-free network with FHN1 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$).	59
4.16	Same as Fig. 4.15 but for FHN2 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$) on BA scale-free network.	59

4.17	Phase diagram showing how the performance of our method depends on the parameters σ and g for the random network with consensus dynamics and $T_{ave} = 1000$. Satisfactory results (both P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} greater than 95%) are represented by open circles and unsatisfactory results by closed circles.	62
4.18	$p_{sen}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{spec}(i)$ (triangles) for the random network (unweighted) with consensus dynamics, $\sigma = g = 1$ and $T_{av} = 1000$ obtained using the generalized algorithm for weighted networks.	68
4.19	The distribution of the normalized coupling strength $P(G)$ inferred using $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ (circles) for the random network with consensus dynamics, $\sigma = g = 1$ and $T_{av} = 1000$. Solid line is a fit of the Gaussian distribution with mean 1 and standard deviation 0.138.	68
4.20	Same as Fig. 4.19 but with $\sigma = 1$, $g = 10$ and $T_{av} = 1000$. Solid line is a fit of the Gaussian distribution with mean 1 and standard deviation 0.0442.	69
4.21	Same as Fig. 4.19 but with $T_{av} = 2000$ (squares) and 10000 (circles) while $\sigma = g = 1$ remains unchanged. Solid line is a fit of the Gaussian distribution with mean 1 and standard deviation 0.0461. Both $T_{av} = 2000$ and 10000 give perfect reconstruction of the network topology with $P_{SEN} = P_{SPEC} = 100\%$	69

4.22	$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for weighted random (WR) network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (b) Rössler dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (c) FHN1 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$), and (d) FHN2 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$).	70
4.23	$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics.	71
4.24	$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) obtained by using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when identifying the separation in the values of r_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics.	71
4.25	$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) obtained by using a longer averaging time $T_{av} = 5000$ for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 and (b) FHN2 dynamics.	72
4.26	The number of false negatives $n_{fn}(i)$ when inferring the links of each node i against $(\min_j g_{ij})/s_i$ for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) Rössler dynamics and (b) FHN1 dynamics.	72
4.27	The number of false positives $n_{fp}(i)$ when inferring the links of each node i against $(\min_j g_{ij})/s_i$ for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) Rössler dynamics and (b) FHN1 dynamics.	73
5.1	$-(\sigma^2/2)C_{ij}^+$ versus g_{ij} for weighted random (WR) network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (b) Rössler dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (c) FHN1 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$), and (d) FHN2 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$). Dashed line is $y = x$	75

5.2	$-(\sigma^2/2)C_{ij}^+$ versus g_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics.	76
5.3	$-(\sigma^2/2)C_{ij}^+$ obtained using $T_{av} = 5000$ versus g_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics.	76
5.4	The inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ against the actual values G_{ij} for weighted random (WR) network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (b) Rössler dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (c) FHN1 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$), and (d) FHN2 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$). The false negatives are labeled in red and the false positives in blue. . .	79
5.5	The inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ against the actual values G_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics. Solid line is fit of the form $y = Dx$	80
5.6	The inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ obtained by using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when identifying the separation in r_{ij} , against the actual values G_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics. Solid line is fit of the form $y = Dx$. .	81
5.7	The inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ obtained using $T_{av} = 5000$ against the actual values G_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics. Solid line is fit of the form $y = Dx$	81

5.8	The inferred normalized node strength $S_i^{(e)}$ (circles) against the actual values S_i for WR network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (b) Rössler dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (c) FHN1 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$), and (d) FHN2 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$).	84
5.9	The inferred normalized node strength $S_i^{(e)}$ (circles) against the actual values S_i for WSF network with (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics. In (c) and (d), we show also the estimate $D'S_i(k_i^{(e)}/\langle k \rangle^{(e)})/(k_i/\langle k \rangle)$ for $S_i^{(e)}$ (triangles).	85
5.10	The inferred average normalized coupling strength of the i -th node $\langle G \rangle_i^{(e)}$ against the actual values $\langle G \rangle_i$ for WSF network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics. Solid line is the fit $y = D'x$	86
5.11	The nodal sensitivity $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ against $\langle G \rangle_i$ for WSF network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics	86
6.1	Comparison of the actual degree distribution $P(k)$ of the BA scale-free network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) consensus dynamics ($\sigma = g = 1$), (b) FHN1 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$), and (c) FHN2 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$).	89
6.2	Comparison of the actual eigenvalue spectrum $\rho(\lambda)$ of the random network (circles) with the inferred spectrum using consensus dynamics with $\sigma = g = 1$ (squares), FHN1 dynamics with $\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$ (triangles), and FHN2 dynamics with $\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$ (diamonds). Solid line is the Wigner semi-circle distribution for the actual spectrum in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$	91

6.3	Comparison of the actual eigenvalue spectrum $\rho(\lambda)$ of the C. elegans neuronal network with the inferred spectrum. The symbols are the same as in Fig. 6.2.	92
6.4	Comparison of the actual eigenvalue spectrum $\rho(\lambda)$ of the BA scale-free network with the inferred spectrum. The symbols are the same as in Fig. 6.2. Solid line is the numerical result from Ref. [74] for the spectrum of BA scale-free network with $N = 5000$ and $m = 2$ averaged over 40 realizations. Dashed line is the inferred spectrum obtained using consensus dynamics with $\sigma = 1$ and a small $g = 0.1$ which is not sufficient to give an accurate reconstruction at $T_{av} = 1000$	92
6.5	Comparison of the actual normalized coupling strength distribution $P(G)$ of the WR network (solid lines) with the inferred distribution using consensus (circles) and Rössler (triangles) dynamics with $\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$ as well as FHN1 (squares) and FHN2 (diamonds) dynamics with $\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$. An averaging time of $T_{av} = 1000$ is used.	94
6.6	Comparison of the actual normalized coupling strength distribution $P(G)$ of the WSF network (solid line) with the inferred distribution using consensus (circles), Rössler (triangles), FHN1 (squares) and FHN2 (diamonds) dynamics. An averaging time of $T_{av} = 1000$ is used for the symbols while the dashed line is the result for FHN2 dynamics with $T_{av} = 5000$	94
6.7	Comparison of the actual degree distribution $P(k)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics.	96

6.8	Comparison of the actual degree distribution $P(k)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics obtained using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when identifying the separation in r_{ij}	97
6.9	Comparison of the actual degree distribution $P(k)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics with the averaging time $T_{av} = 5000$	97
6.10	Comparison of the actual node strength distribution $P(S)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics.	99
6.11	Comparison of the actual node strength distribution $P(S)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics obtained using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when identifying the separation in r_{ij}	100
6.12	Comparison of the actual node strength distribution $P(S)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics with the averaging time $T_{av} = 5000$	100

List of Tables

3.1	Numerical solver used and values of Δt in the simulation of combinations of different networks and dynamics.	43
4.1	Overall sensitivity and specificity of the method for the different unweighted networks and dynamics. Results with the superscript * are obtained without the requirement of $m_0(i) \neq 1$.	49
4.2	Dependence of P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} on the parameters σ , g and T_{av} for the random network with consensus dynamics.	61
4.3	Overall sensitivity P_{SEN} and specificity P_{SPEC} for the unweighted random network with consensus dynamics and the weighted networks with different dynamics. The superscript * denotes results obtained using the criterion for identifying a separation given in Eq. (4.7) instead.	66
5.1	The values of the fitting parameters D and D' for WSF network with FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics. The superscript * denotes results obtained using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when finding the separation in the values of r_{ij}	78

5.2 The average percentage error ξ of $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ for the weighted networks with different dynamics. The superscript * denotes results obtained using the criterion for identifying a separation given in Eq. (4.7) instead. 82

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 An overview of the study of networks

The study of networks has become essential in many scientific disciplines ranging from neuroscience to statistical physics [1–3]. A network consists of elementary components known as nodes that interact through links between the nodes. Examples of networks include the Internet, electric power grid, gene regulatory network and social network. To understand the collective behavior of these systems, it is crucial to know the network connectivity, as the structure is inevitably related to the function of the network. The connectivity of a network can be represented by the adjacency matrix \mathbf{A} . The adjacency matrix element A_{ij} is 1 if node j is linked to node i , otherwise it is 0. As an example, a network with $N = 6$ nodes is shown in Fig. 1.1,

and its adjacency matrix is given by

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.1)$$

where for simplicity we have assumed the network is unweighted, meaning that all links have the same coupling strength. In addition, the network considered is bidirectional, also known as undirected, in which the links are bidirectional in the sense that if a node i affects another node j through a connection, then node j also affects node i . A consequence of this is that $A_{ij} = A_{ji}$ for any pair of nodes i and j . In general, a network can be weighted and/or directed.

Figure 1.1: A network consisting of 6 nodes

Networked dynamical systems have been used extensively to model systems from collection of neurons to array of lasers [4,5]. The simplest network

topologies are provided by geometrically regular networks such as a ring lattice with all nodes linked in a ring pattern or a fully-connected network where each node is connected to all the other nodes. These simple networks have been used to study dynamical complexity in networked nonlinear systems. For example, motivated by the behavior of chemical and biological oscillators, Kuramoto proposed [6] a model of fully-coupled phase oscillators to describe synchronization,

$$\frac{d\theta_i}{dt} = \omega_i + \frac{K}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \sin(\theta_j - \theta_i) \quad (1.2)$$

where $\theta_i(t)$ is the phase of the i oscillator with $i = 1, \dots, N$ and ω_i is its natural frequency drawn randomly from a Lorentz distribution. Although the Kuramoto model is fully nonlinear, it is exactly solvable, and it can be shown that the model exhibits several regimes of synchronization. In particular, when the coupling strength K increases past a critical value K_c , the system goes from an incoherent state to a partially synchronized state where only the oscillators with ω_i close to the mean of the distribution synchronize, and subsequently to a fully synchronized state.

While the simple architecture of regular networks are useful for studying the complexity stemming from the nonlinear dynamics of the nodes, more complex networks have been considered for studying the complexity contributed by network structure. An important class of such networks incorporates stochastic process in their generation. In their pioneering work, Erdős and Rényi developed [7] the Erdős-Rényi (ER) random network model in which each pair of nodes has a probability p to be linked, or similarly, pairs of nodes are chosen at random to be linked until there are m links in the network. Random networks have since been intensely studied and applied to model a wide range of systems such as gene regulatory networks and the spread of computer viruses [8, 9].

Although the random network developed by Erdős and Rényi offered a simple and powerful way to model networks, real-world networks are neither completely random or completely regular. In particular, real networks have a much higher level of clustering than a random network. Let $A - B$ denote a link between nodes A and B . Clustering means that if there are two links $A - B$ and $B - C$, then it is much more likely for $A - C$ to exist. Watts and Strogatz [10] tackled this problem by designing a model that lies between a random network and a regular ring lattice. The Watts-Strogatz (WS) model begins with a regular ring lattice, and replaces links by random ones with a probability ϕ . The rewiring probability ϕ therefore controls the amount of randomness in the network. The resulting network has a high clustering and the average number of intermediate nodes along the shortest path between any two nodes, known as the average path length, is small. Networks with these characteristic properties are known as small-world networks, and many real-world networks from metabolic networks to networks of scientific collaboration fall into this category [11–13]. It is speculated that the short paths between nodes facilitate communication between distant parts of the network and may provide a functional advantage.

Both the ER random network and the Watts-Strogatz model produce a network that is relatively homogeneous. However, in many real networks there exist nodes with a much higher number of connections known as hubs. This effect can be described by defining the node degree $k_i \equiv \sum_j A_{ij}$ which is the total number of connections of a certain node i in the network. The distribution of the node degrees $P(k)$ can then be used to quantify inhomogeneity in the node connections. The random network has a Poisson degree distribution and the WS small-world network has a degree distribution that interpolates between a Dirac delta function and a Poisson distribution, both

are unrealistic in contrast to the highly skewed distributions often observed in real networks. For many real networks, the distribution follows a power law $P(k) \sim k^{-\beta}$ [14–16] and these networks are called scale-free networks. Barabasi and Albert introduced [17] the generative mechanism of "preferential attachment" that they showed can automatically lead to a power-law degree distribution. The Barabasi-Albert (BA) model generates a scale-free network by a stochastic growth process in which new nodes are added step by step, and at each step the newly added node links preferentially to existing nodes with high degree according to a probability that is proportional to the degree of the existing node. It has been further speculated that the scale-free property of networks may serve a function. It has been documented that scale-free networks are resilient to random breakdowns of the nodes [18]. It is because the network only contains a small number of hubs which are functionally important, and it is likely that the random failure would only affect nodes with small degree. On the other hand, this comes at a price as the network would fail when an attack targets the major hubs of the network [19].

To summarize, the study of network is relevant to many disciplines of science, and provides a powerful way to model and understand the behavior of complex systems. Further investigation between the structure and function of networks will be needed. In particular, the speculations that small-world or scale-free properties confer functional advantages will have to be scrutinized.

1.2 The problem of network inference

From the overview in Section 1.1 it is clear that the essential first step of understanding the collective behavior and functionality of a network is to determine its connectivity. However, for many systems it is difficult to directly observe or measure their connectivity. A perfect example would be

neuronal networks in the brain. To identify the connections or synapses between neurons, the brain tissue has to be made into many extremely thin slices which are then imaged with electron microscopy before the three-dimensional structure can be reconstructed [20]. This process is laborious and the reconstruction of the 3-D structure from the 2-D images is computationally formidable. The computational challenge has led researchers turn to strategies such as crowdsourcing, an example of which is the Eye-Wire project involving over 120,000 volunteers who assist in visualizing the 3-D structure [21]. Recent advances include a method that transforms intact tissue into an optically transparent form that can be imaged without disassembly [22]. However, all these methods are still unable to measure the connectivity of living tissues in real-time. On the other hand, the dynamics or activity of a network can often be measured with relative ease. For instance, technologies such as Microelectrode array (MEA) and Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) can simultaneously record brain activity *in vivo* at many locations [23, 24]. Although the spatial resolution of these techniques are generally much lower than electron microscopy and therefore may not be able to resolve the neurons, they may still provide valuable information on the coarse-grained network connectivity of the brain. For example, different methods of defining meaningful nodes from fMRI data have been studied and compared [25]. Thus, a way to infer or reconstruct the structural network from measurements of the dynamics would be highly valuable.

Many methods have been proposed to address this inherently challenging inverse problem, which will be reviewed in Chapter 2. We limit the scope of our work to bidirectional networks and in Chapter 3 we present a novel method of reconstructing bidirectional networks that we have developed and its underlying ideas. Our method can be applied to unweighted and weighted

network, and is capable of reconstructing the connectivity and normalized coupling strength of the network. The accuracy of our method in reconstructing network connectivity is evaluated in Chapter 4 by applying it to simulated dynamical networks. In Chapter 5 we present the reconstruction of normalized coupling strength of weighted networks. We then look at reconstructed global network properties such as eigenvalue spectrum and degree distribution in Chapter 6. Finally, conclusions are given in Chapter 7 and limitations of our method will be discussed, as well as directions for future investigations.

Chapter 2

Review of Existing Methods of Network Reconstruction

A large number of methods have been proposed for network reconstruction, so this chapter is not intended to be an exhaustive summary of these methods, and instead showcases methods in a few broad categories that make use of different ideas. In this chapter we introduce four classes of existing methods for network reconstruction, of which the first two are classical approaches in the field while the latter two are from more recent developments. The first class of method identifies links by employing measures such as statistical correlations [26–29], mutual information [30], or other information-theoretic concepts [31, 32]. The second class uses Bayesian networks [33–35] to search for a network that best matches the joint probability distributions of the measurements. The third class models the probability distribution of the states of the nodes by the Ising model from statistical mechanics and attempts to infer the external fields and the coupling parameters in the model [36–42]. Finally, in the dynamical systems approach networks are modeled by a set of coupled ordinary differential equations and the interactions given by the

couplings in the equations are inferred using different methods [43–48].

2.1 Statistical correlation and information-theoretic measures

A simple and commonly used measure of statistical correlation is the Pearson correlation coefficient which quantifies the linear correlation or dependence between two variables. Suppose we have a network of N nodes with the state of the i -th node given by a single variable $x_i(t)$ at time t , the Pearson correlation between the time series of node i and node j is defined as

$$\Pi_{ij} \equiv \frac{\Sigma_{ij}}{\sqrt{\Sigma_{ii}\Sigma_{jj}}} \quad (2.1)$$

where $\Sigma_{ij} \equiv \langle (x_i - \langle x_i \rangle)(x_j - \langle x_j \rangle) \rangle$ with $\langle \dots \rangle$ being an average over time while Σ_{ii} and Σ_{jj} are the variances of the variables x_i and x_j respectively. The Pearson correlation has been used to reconstruct networks such as the gene-coexpression networks of multiple species [26]. In general, the network is reconstructed using the correlation by identifying a connection between nodes i and j whenever Π_{ij} exceeds a predefined threshold which is set arbitrarily. However, a large Pearson correlation between two nodes is neither a necessary nor a sufficient condition for a connection between them. It is not necessary because the Pearson correlation only measures linear dependence between variables, therefore nonlinear relationships may not be detected. It is also not sufficient since indirect connections, also known as higher-order connections, that link the two nodes through intermediate nodes would also cause a large correlation between them. This results in an incorrectly identified direct connection between the two nodes. The network inferred will therefore have

a high association between indirect paths and direct connections between nodes which is not necessarily true in a general network [49]. In particular, measures based on correlation can hardly differentiate between the cases of two nodes connected by both an indirect path and a direct connection from that of two nodes linked only by an indirect path as represented in Fig. 2.1. Furthermore, the existence of noise would degrade the values of the correlation and extracting the correlation coefficient under heavy noise conditions would be a nontrivial matter [50].

Figure 2.1: Network structure with (a) a direct and high-order connection between nodes u and v , and (b) only an indirect connection between nodes u and v . Figure taken from Ref. [49].

Other similarly motivated measures of correlation have been used, such as the closely related concepts of conditional correlation and partial correlation. The conditional correlation between two variables x_i and x_j given a set of

variables $\vec{\Omega} \equiv (\Omega_1, \Omega_2, \dots, \Omega_p)$ is defined as [51]

$$\Pi_{ij|\vec{\Omega}} \equiv \frac{\Sigma_{ij|\vec{\Omega}}}{\sqrt{\Sigma_{ii|\vec{\Omega}}\Sigma_{jj|\vec{\Omega}}}} \quad (2.2)$$

where $\Sigma_{ij|\vec{\Omega}} \equiv \langle (x_i - \langle x_i|\vec{\Omega} \rangle)(x_j - \langle x_j|\vec{\Omega} \rangle) | \vec{\Omega} \rangle$ with $\langle \dots | \vec{\Omega} \rangle$ denoting an average conditioned on the set of variables $\vec{\Omega}$ and $\Sigma_{qq|\vec{\Omega}}$ is the variance of x_q conditioned on $\vec{\Omega}$. In the context of network reconstruction, the set of variables $\vec{\Omega}$ is given by the dynamics of all the nodes in the network except nodes i and j under consideration, in other words, $\vec{\Omega} = (x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_{j-1}, x_{j+1}, \dots, x_N)$ assuming $i < j$. The conditional correlation has the advantage that it remedies the problem posed by higher-order connections and has close ties with conditional independence [51]. That means a zero conditional correlation between x_i and x_j suggests that they are statistically independent provided that all other x_q ($q \neq i, j$) are fixed. In practice, it is not easy to compute the conditional correlation and its implementation on network reconstruction may have to resort to techniques such as perturbation of the network [27] to generate the required statistics.

The partial correlation is a measure closely related to the conditional correlation. It is defined as the correlation between the residuals R_i and R_j of the linear regression of x_i and x_j with the set of variables $\vec{\Omega}$ respectively. The partial correlation can be easily calculated as it is related to the inverse $\hat{\Sigma}^{-1}$ of the covariance matrix $\hat{\Sigma}$ formed by the elements Σ_{ij} [52]:

$$\rho_{ij} \equiv -\frac{\Sigma_{ij}^{-1}}{\sqrt{\Sigma_{ii}^{-1}\Sigma_{jj}^{-1}}}. \quad (2.3)$$

Partial correlation has been used to infer brain networks from fMRI data [28] and gray matter volumes [29]. However, we caution that the partial

correlation is in general distinct from the conditional correlation and has close ties with conditional independence only when all the variables involved follow a multivariate Gaussian distribution [51].

The measures of statistical dependence above are all linear and may not detect interactions that are nonlinear in nature. For this purpose the mutual information can be utilized. First define the Shannon entropy of a random variable \mathcal{X}

$$H(\mathcal{X}) \equiv - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P(x) \log_2[P(x)] \quad (2.4)$$

and the conditional entropy of the variable \mathcal{X} given variable \mathcal{Y}

$$H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Y}) \equiv - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x, y) \log_2[P(x|y)] \quad (2.5)$$

where $P(x)$ is the probability distribution of \mathcal{X} , $P(x, y)$ is the joint probability distribution of \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} , while $P(x|y)$ is the conditional probability distribution of \mathcal{X} given \mathcal{Y} . Here for simplicity we have assumed that \mathcal{X} takes on discrete values, but the expressions can be readily generalized to the case of continuous variables. The mutual information between two variables \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} is defined as the additional information about \mathcal{X} when given \mathcal{Y} (or vice versa by symmetry). In terms of the entropy and conditional entropy, the mutual information can be written as

$$I(\mathcal{X}; \mathcal{Y}) \equiv H(\mathcal{X}) - H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Y}) = H(\mathcal{Y}) - H(\mathcal{Y}|\mathcal{X}). \quad (2.6)$$

Thus a high mutual information $I(x_i; x_j)$ between the state variables of nodes i and j means that they are not randomly associated with each other, and can be used to measure their interdependence. The mutual information has been applied to reconstruct gene regulatory networks [30]. Unlike linear

correlations, mutual information can uncover both linear and nonlinear relationships. On the other hand, it still suffers from the problem that indirect paths between nodes would result in an association between otherwise unconnected nodes. More sophisticated methods motivated by mutual information have also been used, such as the higher point multi-information defined between the activity of two nodes conditioned on a third node [31] and a more elaborate method based on decomposing the information of a variable into a sum of information-theoretic quantities [32].

2.2 Bayesian network

Consider a system described by a set of n stochastic variables $\vec{\mathcal{X}} \equiv (\mathcal{X}_1, \dots, \mathcal{X}_n)$ that interact among themselves, such as a gene regulatory network with each variable being the expression level of a particular gene. The set of all variables in this system then gives a joint probability distribution $P(\mathcal{X}_1, \dots, \mathcal{X}_n)$ which can be estimated by measuring all the variables for many instances, and would contain information about the statistical dependence or independence between the variables. A Bayesian network is a statistical model that represents the joint probability distribution of a set of random variables by a network structure \hat{G} known as the *directed acyclic graph* (DAG) and a conditional distribution for each variable [34]. The DAG is a network with directional links that does not contain cycles, meaning that there is no way to start at a certain node and travel along the direction of the connections to return to the same beginning node. Each node of DAG represents a variable and its structure embodies the conditional independencies between the variables. Two sets of random variables \vec{A} and \vec{B} are said to be conditionally independent given the set of variables \vec{C} if and only if their conditional

probabilities satisfy

$$P(\vec{A}, \vec{B} | \vec{C}) = P(\vec{A} | \vec{C})P(\vec{B} | \vec{C}). \quad (2.7)$$

In other words, the conditional independencies tell us how the joint probability distribution can be factorized into a product of its constituent conditional distributions. More specifically, the joint probability distribution for a DAG network \hat{G} can be factorized as

$$P(\mathcal{X}_1, \dots, \mathcal{X}_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n P[\mathcal{X}_i | \vec{\mathcal{X}}_{Pa}^{\hat{G}}(\mathcal{X}_i)]. \quad (2.8)$$

Here $\vec{\mathcal{X}}_{Pa}^{\hat{G}}(\mathcal{X}_i)$ denotes the set of parent nodes of \mathcal{X}_i in the network \hat{G} meaning that there is a link from each node in $\vec{\mathcal{X}}_{Pa}^{\hat{G}}(\mathcal{X}_i)$ directed toward the descendant \mathcal{X}_i . Consider the following three examples of Bayesian networks consisting of three variables A , B and C :

$$(1) \quad A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$$

$$(2) \quad A \leftarrow B \rightarrow C$$

$$(3) \quad A \rightarrow B \leftarrow C$$

where $A \rightarrow B$ denotes a directed link that goes from node A to node B . The joint probability distribution $P(A, B, C)$ can be factorized for these networks respectively as

$$(1) \quad P(A, B, C) = P(C|B)P(B|A)P(A)$$

$$(2) \quad P(A, B, C) = P(C|B)P(A|B)P(B)$$

$$(3) \quad P(A, B, C) = P(B|A, C)P(A)P(C).$$

For network (2) above, its factorization is actually identical to that of network (1). This is made apparent by the following derivation:

$$\begin{aligned} & P(C|B)P(A|B)P(B) \\ = & P(C|B)P(A, B) \\ = & P(C|B)P(B|A)P(A) \end{aligned} \tag{2.9}$$

which is just the factorized form for network (1). On the other hand, the factorization of network (3) is truly distinct. Thus multiple networks can lead to the same factorization of the joint probability distribution, or in other terms the same set of conditional independencies. We say that two DAGs are *equivalent* if they imply the same factorization or conditional independencies. As a result, it would be impossible to distinguish between networks that are equivalent using observations of the variables. It has been shown [53] that equivalent DAGs share the same underlying undirected network topology and differs only on the direction of some of the links. Therefore an equivalence class of DAGs can be represented by a *partially directed graph* (PDAG) where a directed link between two nodes means that all networks in the same equivalence class have such a link with the same direction, while an undirected link denotes connection that may have different directions for different member networks.

Given a set of measurements for all the variables taken at different instances, the goal of any Bayesian network inference method is to find an equivalence class of network structure or equivalently the PDAG together with a set of conditional distributions that provide a best match with the joint probability distribution obtained from the measurements. A common

way to proceed is to define a statistical scoring function, such as the posterior probability of the network structure given the measurements, in order to assess the quality of match for each network and to search for the best network that maximizes the score. Methods based on Bayesian network have been used to analyze gene expression data [33, 34] and to study brain networks using fMRI time series [35]. There are several drawbacks of the approach of Bayesian network reconstruction. First of all, the search for the optimal network is underdetermined as the possible networks usually outnumber the measurements [54]. As a result, it would be impossible to single out a unique PDAG if the data is sparse [34]. Another drawback is that the search of networks is computationally intensive as it is shown to be NP-hard [55] and heuristic algorithms have to be relied upon. Lastly, the approach comes with a limitation that it can at best only identify the network up to the level of equivalence class, so causal interpretations of Bayesian network have to be made very carefully. For example, the Bayesian network (1) above is equivalent to network (2) but the two configurations are distinct causal networks. As the reconstruction can only determine the Bayesian network up to its equivalence class or PDAG, it is not capable of revealing the actual causal model among the different networks in the equivalence class.

2.3 Inverse Ising inference

In more recent developments in network reconstruction, the Ising model which originated from the study of ferromagnetism in statistical mechanics has been used as a parametric model for the probability distribution primar-

ily in neural data. The Ising model gives the probability distribution [37]

$$P_I(\vec{s}) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp(\beta \sum_i h_i s_i + \beta \sum_{i<j} J_{ij} s_i s_j) \quad (2.10)$$

where Z is the partition function, $\vec{s} \equiv (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_N)$ and the spin s_i is a binary variable usually taken to represent a spike or the absence of spike in the neuron i . β is the inverse temperature usually set to be 1 without loss of generality, h_i denotes the external field acting on node i and J_{ij} represents the coupling parameter of the interaction between nodes i and j which is taken to be symmetric. Solving the inverse Ising problem amounts to obtaining the external fields h_i and coupling parameters J_{ij} from the probability distribution of the measured data. This is done by fitting the parameters such that the model distribution has the same means and pairwise correlations as the actual data:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle s_i \rangle_I &= \langle s_i \rangle_d, \\ \langle s_i s_j \rangle_I &= \langle s_i s_j \rangle_d \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle_I$ denotes averaging over the Ising model distribution in Eq. (2.10) and $\langle \dots \rangle_d$ means averaging over the measured data. The most straightforward way to find the fields and couplings such that Eq. (2.11) is satisfied is to use an iterative scheme known as Boltzmann learning [37]. The procedure involves setting initial guess values for the parameters, and then calculate the means and correlations of the Ising model using these parameters. The values of the fields h_i and couplings J_{ij} are then modified according to

$$\begin{aligned} \delta h_i &= H[\langle s_i \rangle_d - \langle s_i \rangle_I], \\ \delta J_{ij} &= H[\langle s_i s_j \rangle_d - \langle s_i s_j \rangle_I] \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

where H is the learning rate. The means and correlations are then recalculated using the modified parameters and the entire process is repeated until the model statistics converges to that of the measured data within the accuracy required. Boltzmann learning is an exact method as the parameters always converge to the correct fields and couplings for a sufficiently large number of steps. However, it is computationally very expensive and its complexity is exponential in the network size [36]. As a result, faster approximate methods have been developed. These methods rely on a number of different approximations. For example the naive mean-field (nMF) theory is based on the mean-field equations for the magnetizations and the fluctuation-response relationship which give the following approximation of the mean $m_i \equiv \langle s_i \rangle$ and covariance $\Sigma_{ij} \equiv \langle s_i s_j \rangle - m_i m_j$ [37]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{ij} = \frac{\partial m_i}{\partial h_j} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial h_j} \tanh\left(h_i + \sum_{k=1}^N J_{ik} m_k\right) \\ &= (1 - m_i^2) \left(\delta_{ij} + \sum_{k=1}^N J_{ik} \Sigma_{kj} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

The nMF theory gives the following relationship between the covariance matrix $\hat{\Sigma}$ and the couplings J_{ij} [36]:

$$\Sigma_{ij}^{-1} = \frac{\delta_{ij}}{1 - m_i^2} - J_{ij} \quad (2.14)$$

where Σ_{ij}^{-1} denotes an element of the matrix inverse of $\hat{\Sigma}$. Another approximate method uses the independent pair approximation which involves treating each pair of nodes as independent to the rest of the system [37], and still another method makes use of the inversion of the Thouless-Anderson-Palmer (TAP) equations that relate the local magnetizations to the model parameters [37]. Although these approximate methods provide more efficient means

to infer the network couplings than Boltzmann learning, they are inaccurate for small sample size of data [42] and large subset size of networks [37], which may limit their applicability to only some specific scenarios. Newer developments in inverse Ising inference include the consideration of kinetic Ising models with asymmetric interactions that can model nonequilibrium systems [39–41] and a method based on logistic regression that goes beyond the pairwise correlation and uses all the data available [42]. Nonetheless, current network reconstruction methods based on Ising model still face two main limitations. First, the state variable is assumed to be discrete (usually binary) while for many systems the states are inherently continuous. Secondly, it is still uncertain whether the Ising model is applicable to the many different types of systems encountered in real situations, and a systematic study of its applicability is currently lacking. While relevant work has focused on neural data and the quality of the model has been tested using simulation data from a model network of neurons [37], it remains uncertain whether the model can be generalized to other types of systems.

2.4 Dynamical systems approach

In the dynamical systems approach of network reconstruction, the network is modeled by a set of coupled ordinary differential equations. Consider a network of N nodes with the state of each node given by a d -dimensional state variable $\vec{x}_i \equiv (x_i^{(1)}, x_i^{(2)}, \dots, x_i^{(d)})$ where $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, the general form of the governing equations is given by

$$\frac{d}{dt}\vec{x}_i = \vec{F}_i(\vec{x}_i) + \sum_{j \neq i} g_{ij} A_{ij} \vec{h}(\vec{x}_i, \vec{x}_j) + \vec{n}_i + \vec{I}_i(t) . \quad (2.15)$$

Here \vec{F}_i is the intrinsic dynamics of node i and A_{ij} is an element of the adjacency matrix. If nodes i and j are connected, they are coupled by the function $\vec{h}(\vec{x}_i, \vec{x}_j)$ with coupling strength g_{ij} . There may also be noise affecting the system given by \vec{n}_i or external input denoted as $\vec{\mathcal{I}}_i(t)$.

There is a myriad of different network reconstruction methods based on dynamical systems depending on how the network is modeled and the dynamical properties that is focused upon. Nonetheless, they can be broadly categorized into two types. The first type requires external perturbation or stimulus applied to the network, and the second type employs the spontaneous activity of the network without external driving ($\vec{\mathcal{I}}_i(t) = 0$). In the following, we will give an overview of a number of different methods from each category.

One method that falls into the first category focuses on the reconstruction of gene regulatory networks and assumes a linear system of ordinary differential equations [43]. In each measurement, a prescribed stimulus ($\mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2, \dots, \mathcal{I}_N$) is given to the N nodes of the network and the dynamics of the nodes x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N is measured simultaneously. This is repeated a number of times and for P measurements of the N nodes, the equations of motion can be rewritten into a $(N \times P)$ matrix equation involving the measured dynamics and the known stimuli. It is typical that $P \ll N$ since the perturbations and measurements are often costly. As a result, the matrix equation is underdetermined and the *singular value decomposition* (SVD) is used to find a particular solution of the problem. The general solution is then expressed in terms of the particular solution. As the solutions are not unique, an additional constraint of the sparseness of typical gene networks is used to arrive at the final solution. We comment that the restriction to linear systems and sparse networks limits the applicability of this method as many real networks

are governed by nonlinear dynamics and may not necessarily be sparse.

Another similar method applies a temporally constant driving $\mathcal{I}_{i,m}$ where m denotes the driving condition [44]. The stationary response of the network is then measured. The measurements are repeated P times using linearly independent driving conditions, and again this results in a $(N \times P)$ matrix equation that is solved by singular value decomposition. A sparseness condition is also required to deduce a unique set of network connectivity, so this method shares the same fundamental weakness of the last method that it is only applicable to sparse networks.

Still another method that utilizes perturbation involves obtaining an ensemble of initial data by repeated reinitializations of the network dynamics [45]. The reinitialization is proposed to be achieved by the phenomenon of phase resetting in limit cycle oscillators under external perturbation. In such a case, the perturbation shifts the phase of the oscillators and can reinitialize the network to independent initial conditions. A reconstruction measure is then computed from the ensemble of initial data and used to infer the network connectivity. The advantage of this method over the previous two methods is that it no longer requires the network to be sparse. However, although the method does not explicitly restrict the type of dynamics of the network, it hinges on the assumption that such a reinitialization can be achieved, and thus places an implicit constraint on the dynamics. The technique of random phase reset is most relevant to biological oscillators that is well described by limit cycles, but it is unclear whether the reinitialization can be achieved in other types of systems.

In general, methods that rely on external perturbations suffer from the disadvantage that such perturbations may be expensive or even impossible to carry out in many real systems. Therefore another class of network in-

ference methods remove this requirement and attempts to reconstruct the network from its spontaneous activity. Below we discuss a few examples of this approach.

In the method proposed in Ref. [46], an artificial network is introduced that has the same intrinsic dynamics and coupling function to the original network of interest with unknown connectivity. The connectivity of the artificial network is varied in time according to a set of ordinary differential equations involving the measured dynamics of the original network such that its dynamics becomes synchronized with the original network. The connectivity of the synchronized artificial network is then identified as that of the original network. This method assumes that both the equations of motion and the coupling function are known, which is generally not the case for real networks being studied. It has further been shown that [47] when such information is available, the network connectivity can simply be obtained by approximating the state variables and their derivatives in the governing equations at different time points using the time series and then inferring the network connectivity from the resulting matrix equation by least squares optimization.

Finally, another study reveals that the existence of noise induces a relation between the dynamical covariance of the measured time series of the nodes and the network connectivity [48]. This relation is then used to reconstruct the network connectivity. However, the procedure proposed by the authors requires explicit use of the noise amplitude and coupling strength, which is generally not known *a priori* for the networks to be reconstructed.

Throughout this chapter, we have seen that existing methods of network reconstruction either suffer from issues caused by indirect paths between nodes, the underdetermined nature of the problem, high computational cost,

or the requirement of additional information such as the response to external perturbations and the functional form of the governing equations which is difficult to acquire in realistic scenarios. In response to these inadequate methods, we have developed a novel method of network inference that requires only the measured dynamics of the nodes and is shown to be applicable to general dynamics without restriction to the specific network connectivity. Our method will be discussed in detail in Chapter 3.

Chapter 3

A Novel Method of Network Reconstruction

In this chapter, we present a novel method that reconstructs network connectivity and normalized coupling strength using only measurements of the nodal dynamics [56, 57]. Our method is built upon a noise-induced relation between the dynamical covariance of the nodes and the network connectivity. This chapter is organized as follows. In Section 3.1, the problem will be set up and the theory introduced. In particular, an analytical derivation will be given for the exact relation between the dynamical covariance and connectivity under the assumption of a particular dynamics known as the consensus dynamics [58]. Based on this relation, we then develop our method of network reconstruction. There is evidence from numerical simulations [48] that supports this relation is applicable even for the case of general intrinsic dynamics. Therefore we propose to apply our method to other types of dynamics as well. Section 3.2 concerns the reconstruction of network topology and we will present a way to distinguish the links from unconnected pairs of nodes. Finally, in Section 3.3 we discuss how the normalized coupling

strength of weighted networks can be inferred.

3.1 The theory

In accordance with the dynamical systems approach of network reconstruction, we model the time evolution of the network with a set of coupled ordinary differential equations. We assume that the intrinsic dynamics $\vec{F}_i = \vec{f}$ is identical for all the nodes. Without loss of generality, we apply noise only to the first element of the state variable $x_i(t) \equiv x_i^{(1)}(t)$ and uses it for reconstruction. We also consider the spontaneous activity of the system without external driving, as such intervention is often not possible in realistic situations. Under these assumptions, Eq. (2.15) can be written as

$$\frac{d}{dt}\vec{x}_i = \vec{f}(\vec{x}_i) + \sum_{j \neq i} g_{ij} A_{ij} \vec{h}(\vec{x}_i, \vec{x}_j) + \eta_i \vec{e}_1 \quad (3.1)$$

where the vector $\vec{e}_1 = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$ as the noise is only applied to the first element of the state variable. η_i is a Gaussian white noise with zero mean and variance σ^2 and has the following property,

$$\overline{\eta_i(t)\eta_j(t')} = \sigma^2 \delta_{ij} \delta(t - t') \quad (3.2)$$

with the overbar being an average over noise. We assume that the network has only one connected component and self-loops are absent such that the diagonal elements of the adjacency matrix $A_{ii} = 0$. As we consider networks that are bidirectional, we also have $A_{ij} = A_{ji}$ and $g_{ij} = g_{ji}$.

The aim of the reconstruction is to infer A_{ij} and g_{ij} using only the measured dynamics $\vec{x}_i(t)$ of the nodes. It can be shown that noise induces a relation between the dynamical covariance and network connectivity [48, 56].

The dynamical covariance between nodes i and j is defined as

$$C_{ij} = \langle [x_i(t) - X(t)][x_j(t) - X(t)] \rangle_T \quad (3.3)$$

where $X(t) \equiv (1/N) \sum_{i=1}^N x_i(t)$ is the average activity of the entire network and $\langle \dots \rangle_T$ is an average over time T . Here we derive an exact result for consensus dynamics [58] with the dimension of the state variable $d = 1$, $f(x_i) = 0$ and linear diffusive coupling $h(x_i, x_j) = x_j - x_i$. Note that although an analytical proof exists only for this specific linear dynamics, we propose to apply it as an approximation for the case of general dynamics and will subsequently use it to reconstruct networks in the general case. For consensus dynamics, Eq. (3.1) simplifies to

$$\frac{d}{dt}x_i = \sum_{j=1}^N g_{ij}A_{ij}(x_j - x_i) + \eta_i = -\langle g \rangle \sum_{j=1}^N M_{ij}x_j + \eta_i \quad (3.4)$$

$$M_{ij} = \frac{s_i}{\langle g \rangle} \delta_{ij} - \frac{g_{ij}A_{ij}}{\langle g \rangle} \quad (3.5)$$

where $\langle g \rangle$ is the average coupling strength of all the links and s_i is the strength of node i defined as the sum of the coupling strengths of all links in node i .

$$\langle g \rangle \equiv \frac{\sum_{i,j} g_{ij}A_{ij}}{\sum_{i,j} A_{ij}}, \quad s_i \equiv \sum_{j=1}^N g_{ij}A_{ij} \quad (3.6)$$

The matrix \hat{M} contains information of the network connectivity and coupling strength. Furthermore, for unweighted network with $g_{ij} = g$ it reduces to the commonly used Laplacian matrix \hat{L} defined by $L_{ij} \equiv k_i \delta_{ij} - A_{ij}$. Note that the matrix \hat{M} has the property that the sum of any row or column is

equal to zero:

$$\sum_{j=1}^N M_{ij} = \sum_{i=1}^N M_{ij} = 0. \quad (3.7)$$

This implies that \hat{M} has a null eigenvalue with eigenvector $\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}(1, 1, \dots, 1)$. In addition, the number of zero eigenvalues would be equal to the number of connected components of the network, so for a network with a single connected component there is only one zero eigenvalue. Consider diagonalization of the matrix \hat{M} :

$$\hat{P}^T \hat{M} \hat{P} = \hat{\Lambda}. \quad (3.8)$$

where \hat{P} is the square matrix with the i -th column being the i -th unit eigenvector of \hat{M} and $\hat{\Lambda} \equiv \text{Diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_N)$ is the diagonal matrix containing the eigenvalues in ascending order. We have used the fact that \hat{P} is orthogonal as \hat{M} is symmetric. The zero eigenvalue is given by $\lambda_1 = 0$, so Eq. (3.8) becomes

$$\hat{M} = \hat{P} \hat{\Lambda} \hat{P}^T \Rightarrow \hat{M}^+ = \hat{P} \hat{D} \hat{P}^T \quad (3.9)$$

where \hat{D} is the diagonal matrix with $D_{11} = 0$ and $D_{ii} = 1/\lambda_i$ for $i \neq 1$ and the superscript $+$ denotes the Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse of a matrix, which is a generalization of the inverse matrix. It follows that

$$M_{ij}^+ = \sum_{k=2}^N \frac{P_{ik} P_{jk}}{\lambda_k}. \quad (3.10)$$

From Eq. (3.7), we have

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \sum_{ij} M_{ij} = \sum_i \sum_k P_{ik} \lambda_k \sum_j P_{jk} = \sum_k \lambda_k \left(\sum_j P_{jk} \right)^2 \\ &\Rightarrow \sum_j P_{jk} = 0, \quad \forall k \neq 1. \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

Note that the derivation in Eq. (3.11) requires \hat{P} to be orthogonal, so it would be valid only for bidirectional networks with \hat{M} being symmetric.

To obtain an expression for the dynamical covariance, we need to solve for $x_i(t)$. In vector form, Eq. (3.4) can be written as

$$\frac{d}{dt}\vec{x} = -\langle g \rangle \hat{M}\vec{x} + \vec{\eta}. \quad (3.12)$$

Therefore the solution is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{x}(t) &= e^{-\langle g \rangle t \hat{M}} \vec{x}(0) + \int_0^t dt' e^{-\langle g \rangle (t-t') \hat{M}} \vec{\eta}(t') \\ &= \hat{P} e^{-\langle g \rangle t \hat{\Lambda}} \hat{P}^T \vec{x}(0) + \int_0^t dt' \hat{P} e^{-\langle g \rangle (t-t') \hat{\Lambda}} \hat{P}^T \vec{\eta}(t'). \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

Equivalently, that means the state of the i -th node $x_i(t)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} x_i(t) &= \sum_{k,s} e^{-\langle g \rangle t \lambda_k} P_{ik} P_{sk} x_s(0) \\ &\quad + \sum_{k,s} \int_0^t dt' \eta_s(t') e^{-\langle g \rangle (t-t') \lambda_k} P_{ik} P_{sk}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

Now we proceed to calculate the dynamical covariance between nodes i and j . By expanding Eq. (3.3) and taking an average over noise, we have

$$\overline{C_{ij}} = \overline{\langle X(t)^2 \rangle}_T + \overline{\langle x_i(t) x_j(t) \rangle}_T - \overline{\langle x_i(t) X(t) \rangle}_T - \overline{\langle x_j(t) X(t) \rangle}_T \quad (3.15)$$

Using Eqs. (3.14) and (3.2) together with the orthogonality of \hat{P} , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{X(t)^2} &= \frac{1}{N^2} \left[\sum_{l,k,s} e^{-\langle g \rangle t \lambda_k} P_{lk} P_{sk} x_s(0) \right]^2 \\ &+ \frac{\sigma^2}{N^2} \sum_k I_k(t) \sum_l (P_{lk})^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{x_i x_j} &= \sum_{k,k',s,s'} e^{-\langle g \rangle t (\lambda_k + \lambda_{k'})} P_{ik} P_{jk'} P_{sk} P_{s'k'} x_s(0) x_{s'}(0) \\ &+ \sigma^2 \sum_k I_k(t) P_{ik} P_{jk} \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{x_i(t) X(t)} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l,k,k',s,s'} e^{-\langle g \rangle t (\lambda_k + \lambda_{k'})} P_{ik} P_{lk'} P_{sk} P_{s'k'} x_s(0) x_{s'}(0) \\ &+ \frac{\sigma^2}{N} \sum_k I_k(t) \sum_l P_{lk} P_{ik} \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

where

$$I_k(t) \equiv \int_0^t dt' e^{-2\langle g \rangle \lambda_k (t-t')}. \quad (3.19)$$

Therefore the dynamical covariance can be written as a sum of two terms $\overline{C_{ij}} = \langle S_{ij}^{(1)}(t) + S_{ij}^{(2)}(t) \rangle_T$ where $S_{ij}^{(2)}(t)$ contains the terms with the coefficient σ^2 and $S_{ij}^{(1)}(t)$ contains the remaining terms. The two terms are given by

$$\begin{aligned} S_{ij}^{(1)}(t) &= \sum_{k,k',s,s'} e^{-\langle g \rangle (\lambda_k + \lambda_{k'}) t} P_{sk} P_{s'k'} x_s(0) x_{s'}(0) \\ &\times (P_{ik} - \frac{1}{N} \sum_l P_{lk}) (P_{jk'} - \frac{1}{N} \sum_l P_{lk'}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.20)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{ij}^{(2)}(t) &= \sigma^2 \sum_k I_k(t) \left\{ \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_l (P_{lk})^2 + P_{ik} P_{jk} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{2}{N} \sum_l P_{lk} (P_{ik} + P_{jk}) \right\} \\
 &= \sigma^2 \sum_{k=1}^N I_k(t) \left(P_{ik} - \frac{1}{N} \sum_l P_{lk} \right) \left(P_{jk} - \frac{1}{N} \sum_l P_{lk} \right). \quad (3.21)
 \end{aligned}$$

From Eq. (3.11) and $P_{m1} = 1/\sqrt{N}$ for all m implied by the eigenvector $\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}(1, 1, \dots, 1)$ of the null eigenvalue, the following relation can be obtained.

$$P_{ik} - \frac{1}{N} \sum_l P_{lk} = \begin{cases} 0 & k = 1 \\ P_{ik} & k \neq 1 \end{cases} \quad (3.22)$$

Therefore Eqs. (3.20) and (3.21) can be simplified to

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{ij}^{(1)}(t) &= \sum_{k,k'=2} e^{-\langle g \rangle (\lambda_k + \lambda_{k'}) t} P_{ik} P_{jk'} \\
 &\quad \times \sum_{s,s'} P_{sk} P_{s'k'} x_s(0) x_{s'}(0) \quad (3.23)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$S_{ij}^{(2)}(t) = \frac{\sigma^2}{2\langle g \rangle} \sum_{k=2}^N \frac{1 - e^{-2\langle g \rangle \lambda_k t}}{\lambda_k} P_{ik} P_{jk}. \quad (3.24)$$

In the limit of long-time averaging $T \rightarrow \infty$, we may take $t \rightarrow \infty$ in Eqs. (3.23) and (3.24), yielding

$$S_{ij}^{(1)}(t) \rightarrow 0 \quad (3.25)$$

and

$$S_{ij}^{(2)}(t) \rightarrow \frac{\sigma^2}{2\langle g \rangle} \sum_{k=2}^N \frac{P_{ik} P_{jk}}{\lambda_k} = \frac{\sigma^2}{2\langle g \rangle} M_{ij}^+ \quad (3.26)$$

Here we have applied Eq. (3.10). Finally, we get

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \overline{C_{ij}} = S_{ij}^{(1)}(t \rightarrow \infty) + S_{ij}^{(2)}(t \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{\sigma^2}{2\langle g \rangle} M_{ij}^+ . \quad (3.27)$$

Taking pseudoinverse on both sides of Eq. (3.27) and approximate $\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \overline{C_{ij}}$ by C_{ij} with a finite $T = T_{av}$, we have

$$M_{ij} \approx \frac{\sigma^2}{2\langle g \rangle} C_{ij}^+ . \quad (3.28)$$

In Eq. (3.28), the term M_{ij} contains the information of network connectivity and coupling strength while C_{ij}^+ can be calculated using the dynamics of the nodes, therefore this relation bridges the measured dynamics with the network connectivity. Taking the off-diagonal elements of Eq. (3.28) and using Eq. (3.5), we have

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} C_{ij}^+ \approx -g_{ij}, \quad i \neq j . \quad (3.29)$$

Note that this equation is highly similar to the off-diagonal parts of Eq. (2.14), differing only on a proportionality constant. Since Eq. (2.14) was derived in a completely different way using the mean-field equations of the Ising model, we expect our result in Eq. (3.29) should hold a certain level of generality. On the other hand, we also emphasize that our result goes beyond the result in Eq. (2.14) obtained from inverse Ising inference in two ways. First, our result is derived for continuous state variables rather than binary or discrete variables. This is important as many systems exhibit states that are continuous and cannot be meaningfully transformed into binary states. Secondly, as we will show in Chapter 4, our result can be applied to different types of dynamics and coupling for reconstruction with high accuracy instead

of relying on the applicability of a single model to work. For unweighted networks with $g_{ij} = g$, \hat{M} reduces to the Laplacian matrix \hat{L} , so Eq. (3.28) becomes

$$L_{ij} \approx \frac{\sigma^2}{2g} C_{ij}^+. \quad (3.30)$$

The relation in Eq. (3.30) was first presented in Ref. [48] and an analytical proof was given in Ref. [56] for consensus dynamics. Numerical results in Ref. [48] suggest that the relation is applicable even for general dynamics. In Sections 3.2 and 3.3 we proceed to show how Eq. (3.28) can be used to reconstruct the network connectivity and normalized coupling strength respectively.

3.2 Method for Reconstruction of Connectivity

Equation (3.28) contains the noise amplitude σ and the average coupling strength $\langle g \rangle$ which are not known *a priori*, we therefore eliminate this explicit dependence by taking the ratio of the off-diagonal elements to the diagonal elements in the matrix relation:

$$r_{ij} \equiv \frac{C_{ij}^+}{C_{ii}^+} \approx \frac{M_{ij}}{M_{ii}} = \begin{cases} -\frac{g_{ij}}{s_i}, & A_{ij} = 1 \\ 0, & A_{ij} = 0 \end{cases} \quad \text{for } i \neq j. \quad (3.31)$$

Thus for each node i , the values of r_{ij} ($j \neq i$) would separate into two groups, the first group has negative values corresponding to those nodes j that are connected to i , and the second group has values close to zero which corresponds to the remaining nodes j that are unconnected to i . The network connectivity can then be reconstructed by locating the separation in

the values of r_{ij} for each node i . In order to carry out this process efficiently, we automate the process by using algorithms to find the separation. In particular, we have developed an algorithm for unweighted network which will be presented in Section 3.2.1. We subsequently generalize the algorithm in Section 3.2.2 to make it applicable to weighted networks.

3.2.1 Algorithm for unweighted networks

For unweighted networks, $g_{ij} = g$ and Eq. (3.31) simplifies to

$$r_{ij} \equiv \frac{C_{ij}^+}{C_{ii}^+} \approx \frac{L_{ij}}{L_{ii}} = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{k_i}, & A_{ij} = 1 \\ 0, & A_{ij} = 0 \end{cases} \quad \text{for } i \neq j. \quad (3.32)$$

Thus for all the nodes j that are linked to node i , r_{ij} will have values close to each other in the order $-1/k_i$, and we can apply the following procedures to identify the separation.

- (1) Calculate r_{ij} for $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $j \neq i$.
- (2) For each node i , sort the $N - 1$ values of r_{ij} and arrange them in ascending order. The m -th smallest value of r_{ij} is denoted as $r_i(m)$. As $r_i(m) \sim -1/k_i$ for the nodes connected to node i and $r_i(m) \sim 0$ for the unconnected nodes, we expect that when we increase m , at a certain point $m = m_0(i)$ there would be a large difference between $r_i(m + 1)$ and $r_i(m)$. Once we identify $m_0(i)$, the nodes j with r_{ij} corresponding to $r_i(m)$ for $1 \leq m \leq m_0(i)$ are deduced to be connected to node i , and the remaining nodes are deduced to be unconnected to node i .
- (3) Calculate the difference $d_i(m) \equiv r_i(m + 1) - r_i(m)$ for each m and identify $m_0(i)$ as the value of m at which $d_i(m)$ attains maximum provided

that the following two criteria are satisfied: (i) the maximum value of $d_i(m)$ exceeds two times the second-largest value, and (ii) $r_i(m) < 0$.

- (4) If the above two conditions are not both satisfied, $m_0(i)$ is taken to be the value $m < N - 1$ at which the sum $\sum_{n=1}^m r_i(n)$ is closest to -1 . This is from the result of summing Eq. (3.32) over $j \neq i$.
- (5) The quality of separation can be measured by comparing $d_i[m_0(i)]$ to the average separation given by $[r_i(N-1) - r_i(1)]/(N-2)$. We therefore compute the following parameter for the comparison.

$$\delta(i) \equiv \frac{r_i[m_0(i) + 1] - r_i[m_0(i)]}{[r_i(N-1) - r_i(1)]/(N-2)} \quad (3.33)$$

When $\delta(i)$ is sufficiently large, there is clear separation of r_{ij} into two groups and we expect the accuracy of the reconstruction would be high. An overall measure of the expected accuracy of the inferred network connectivity can further be obtained by averaging $\delta(i)$ over all the nodes:

$$\Delta \equiv \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta(i). \quad (3.34)$$

A high value of Δ indicates that there is clear separation in r_{ij} for different nodes i , and we expect in such case the overall accuracy would be satisfactory.

- (6) In the scenario that the connectivity information between any pair of nodes i and j inferred using r_{im} ($m \neq i$) is in conflict with that inferred using r_{jm} ($m \neq j$), we compare $\delta(i)$ with $\delta(j)$ and the information obtained from the node with a larger δ shall prevail.

3.2.2 Algorithm for weighted networks

For weighted networks with non-uniform g_{ij} , Eq. (3.31) implies that for a fixed i the values of r_{ij} would depend on g_{ij} and therefore varies for different nodes j that are linked to node i . The values of r_{ij} will then depend on the distribution of g_{ij} and the difference separating the connected and unconnected values of r_{ij} may not be the largest. Therefore we generalize the algorithm by modifying step (3) of the procedures for unweighted networks. The modified algorithm is given by the following.

- (1) Calculate r_{ij} for $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $j \neq i$.
- (2) For each node i , sort the $N - 1$ values of r_{ij} and arrange them in ascending order: $[r_i(1), r_i(2), \dots, r_i(m), \dots, r_i(N - 1)]$. We then need to identify $m_0(i)$ in order to separate the connections from the unconnected nodes.
- (3) Calculate the difference $d_i(m)$ for each m and compute the mean and standard deviation of $d_i(m)$, denoted by $\langle d_i \rangle$ and ζ_i respectively. Identify $m_0(i)$ as the largest value of m such that: (i) $d_i(m) - \langle d_i \rangle > 2\zeta_i$ and (ii) $r_i(m) < 0$.
- (4) If the above two conditions are not simultaneously satisfied for any m , we take $m_0(i)$ to be the value $m < N - 1$ such that $\sum_{n=1}^m r_i(n)$ is closest to -1 .
- (5) The value of $\delta(i)$ is computed for each node i using Eq. (3.33).
- (6) In case of conflict between the connectivity information inferred from r_{im} ($m \neq i$) and r_{jm} ($m \neq j$), the result from the node with a higher value of δ is used.

3.3 Method for Reconstruction of Normalized Coupling Strength and Node Strength

For weighted networks, it is important to also have information about the coupling strength g_{ij} and node strength s_i apart from the network connectivity. Such information can be obtained from Eq. (3.29). We eliminate the noise strength σ by using the normalized coupling strength G_{ij} and normalized node strength S_i defined as

$$G_{ij} \equiv \frac{g_{ij}}{\langle g \rangle}, \quad S_i \equiv \frac{s_i}{\langle s \rangle} = \frac{\sum_j G_{ij} A_{ij}}{\langle k \rangle}, \quad (3.35)$$

where $\langle s \rangle \equiv \sum_i s_i/N$ and $\langle k \rangle \equiv \sum_i k_i/N$ are the average node strength and average node degree respectively. Using Eqs. (3.29) and (3.35), G_{ij} and S_i can then be inferred by

$$G_{ij}^{(e)} = \frac{C_{ij}^+ \sum_l k_l^{(e)}}{\sum_{n, l \leftrightarrow n} C_{nl}^+}, \quad S_i^{(e)} = \frac{N \sum_{j \leftrightarrow i} C_{ij}^+}{\sum_{n, l \leftrightarrow n} C_{nl}^+} \quad (3.36)$$

Here $k_i^{(e)} \equiv \sum_j A_{ij}^{(e)}$ is the inferred degree of node i with $A_{ij}^{(e)}$ being the reconstructed adjacency matrix and $\sum_{l \leftrightarrow n}$ is defined as a sum over all the nodes l that are inferred to be connected to node n ($A_{ln}^{(e)} = 1$).

3.4 Evaluating the method

We evaluate our method by applying it to systems described by Eq. (3.1) on different networks. The first set of networks tested are unweighted networks with $g_{ij} = g$: (i) a random network of $N = 100$ nodes with connection probability $p = 0.2$, (ii) the neuronal network of the roundworm *Caenorhabditis elegans* (C. elegans) with $N = 279$ which has been simplified by treating

all connections as uniform and bidirectional, and (iii) a BA scale-free network [17] with $N = 1000$.

We have also tested our method on weighted networks including (i) weighted random (WR) networks of $N = 100$ nodes which is a random network with Gaussian distributed coupling strength g_{ij} with mean μ and standard deviation γ , and (ii) a weighted scale-free (WSF) network [59] with $N = 1000$.

We have mentioned earlier in this chapter that there is numerical evidence that the relation our method is based on is applicable even for general dynamics. Therefore we propose to apply our method to general dynamics and obtain support for its applicability by studying other intrinsic dynamics apart from the consensus dynamics. These include the nonlinear FitzHugh-Nagumo (FHN) model [60], which was first proposed to study the excitable dynamics of neurons. The FHN model for a single neuron consists of two variables ($d = 2$), a fast voltage-like variable x and a slow variable y that describes the recovery of the neuron:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x} &= \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(x - \frac{x^3}{3} - y \right) + \mathcal{I} \\ \dot{y} &= x + \alpha\end{aligned}\tag{3.37}$$

where α and ϵ are parameters in the model and \mathcal{I} is an external input. For $|\alpha| > 1$, the system displays excitable dynamics, meaning that when \mathcal{I} exceeds a certain threshold value, the system exhibits a typical large-amplitude excursion in phase space known as a spike and then relaxes back to its resting state. On the other hand, when $|\alpha| < 1$ the system has an oscillatory dynamics characterized by a spontaneous and persistent periodic motion. The factor ϵ gives the difference in time scale between the fast and slow variable. We consider a network of FHN elements coupled through the

fast variable while the external input is replaced by a noise term:

$$\dot{x}_i = \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(x_i - \frac{x_i^3}{3} - y_i \right) + \sum_{j \neq i} g_{ij} A_{ij} (x_j - x_i) + \eta_i, \quad (3.38)$$

$$\dot{y}_i = x_i + \alpha. \quad (3.39)$$

We set $\epsilon = 0.01$ for our simulations and use two different values of α : 1.05 (excitable) and 0.95 (oscillatory). We denote the former as FHN1 dynamics and the latter as FHN2 dynamics.

To test whether our method is applicable to coupling forms other than the linear diffusive coupling $h(x_i, x_j) = x_j - x_i$, we considered the case of a cubic coupling form $h(x_i, x_j) = (x_j - x_i)^3$ with zero intrinsic dynamics $f(x_i) = 0$:

$$\frac{d}{dt} x_i = \sum_{j=i}^N g_{ij} A_{ij} (x_j - x_i)^3 + \eta_i. \quad (3.40)$$

We have also studied a combination of both nonlinear intrinsic dynamics and coupling function using the Rössler dynamics [61] ($d = 3$) with nonlinear coupling of the hyperbolic tangent form:

$$\dot{x}_i = -y_i - z_i + \sum_{j \neq i} g_{ij} A_{ij} \tanh(x_j - x_i) + \eta_i \quad (3.41)$$

$$\dot{y}_i = x_i + a y_i + \sum_{j \neq i} g_{ij} A_{ij} \tanh(y_j - y_i) \quad (3.42)$$

$$\dot{z}_i = b + z_i(x_i - c) + \sum_{j \neq i} g_{ij} A_{ij} \tanh(z_j - z_i) \quad (3.43)$$

with $a = b = 0.2$ and $c = 9$. The Rössler system exhibits chaotic behavior when uncoupled.

Finally, we attempt to delineate the effect of non-identical intrinsic dynamics using the Kuramoto phase oscillators in Eq. (1.2) but with specified network connectivity and coupling strength rather than the fully-coupled

case originally considered by Kuramoto. The governing equations then read

$$\frac{d\theta_i}{dt} = \omega_i + \sum_{j=1}^N g_{ij} A_{ij} \sin(\theta_j - \theta_i) + \eta_i. \quad (3.44)$$

Here the natural frequencies of the nodes ω_i is different for each node and is drawn from the Lorentz distribution $P(\omega) = 1/[\pi(1 + \omega^2)]$. The Kuramoto phase oscillator is also useful to give insights on the relationship between synchronization and the accuracy of our method, as the order parameters $R(t)$ and $\Psi(t)$ can be readily calculated using

$$R(t)e^{i\Psi(t)} \equiv \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N e^{i\theta_j(t)} \quad (3.45)$$

where $R(t)$ gives the phase coherence and therefore the level of synchronization of the network at time t while $\Psi(t)$ is the mean phase of the network at time t . A perfectly synchronized network would have $R = 1$.

As described earlier, we identify the network links by calculating r_{ij} and then finding the separation in the values of r_{ij} into two groups for each i using the two algorithms for unweighted and weighted networks respectively. We detail the simulation procedures for the various cases studied in Sections 3.4.1 and 3.4.2 for the unweighted networks and weighted networks respectively.

3.4.1 Simulating the unweighted networks

As mentioned earlier, three unweighted networks are tested. The first network is a random network with connection probability $p = 0.2$ between any pair of nodes. Each independent entry of the adjacency matrix $A_{ij} = A_{ji}$ is chosen randomly to be 1 (with probability p) or 0 (with probability $1 - p$) using a pseudorandom generator. The random network serves as a control

that can be compared to other networks with nontrivial structures. The second network is the neuronal network of *C. elegans* which is a small-world network [10, 62]. The network connectivity is obtained from the WormAtlas online database [63] and the $N = 279$ non-pharyngeal neurons of the somatic nervous system are included while the pharyngeal neurons and the neuromuscular junctions (NMJs) are omitted. We simplify this network by treating all the electrical and chemical synapses as identical and bidirectional. Finally, a BA scale-free network [17] with $N = 1000$ is generated by the following procedures with the parameter $m = 2$:

- (1) Starting with a small number m_0 of unconnected nodes, at the first step, add a new node with $m = m_0$ links such that all existing nodes are connected to the newly added node. We choose $m = m_0$ to ensure that no nodes have zero degree after the first step.
- (2) Starting from the second step, new nodes with $m = m_0$ links are added with the connection probability $p_i = k_i / \sum_j k_j$, i.e. the new node connects preferentially to existing nodes with a high degree.
- (3) After t steps, a network with $N = t + m_0$ nodes and mt links is formed.

For the unweighted networks, we carried out simulation for consensus dynamics with $\sigma = g = 1$ and for FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics with $\sigma = 1$, $g = 10$. The cubic coupling form and Kuramoto phase oscillators are further studied on the random network. In order to study the effect of noise and coupling strength on the accuracy of our method, we have tested additional sets of values of σ and g on the random network with consensus dynamics. We integrate the coupled differential equations of these systems in time with the Euler-Maruyama method [64] using $\Delta t = 5 \times 10^{-4}$ and the initial condition of each $x_i(t = 0)$ is randomly assigned a value from 0 to 1. The numerical

methods are described in detail in Appendix A.

After solving for the time series $x_i(t)$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, we use it to calculate the dynamical covariance C_{ij} by averaging over the time T_{av} at sampling interval of 5×10^{-4} . We take $T_{av} = 1000$ unless otherwise specified. The next step involves calculating the pseudoinverse \hat{C}^+ of the matrix \hat{C} . A standard way to calculate the pseudoinverse is by construction using the singular value decomposition (SVD). Consider the SVD of a general $(m \times n)$ matrix \hat{A} :

$$\hat{A} = \hat{U} \hat{S} \hat{V}^T \quad (3.46)$$

where the columns of \hat{U} consist of the left singular vectors, the rows of \hat{V}^T are the right singular vectors, and \hat{S} is a diagonal matrix formed by the singular values. After that, the pseudoinverse is given by

$$\hat{A}^+ = \hat{V} \hat{S}^+ \hat{U}^T. \quad (3.47)$$

The pseudoinverse \hat{S}^+ can be readily calculated by taking the reciprocal of all the non-zero diagonal elements while keeping the zero ones unchanged. In practice, this requires setting a tolerance below which a singular value is regarded as zero. Following the treatment in the MATLAB pseudoinverse function *pinv*, we set the tolerance to be $\tau = \epsilon \max(m, n) \max(\hat{S})$ with ϵ being the machine epsilon. Note that as the matrix \hat{C} is a $(N \times N)$ square matrix that is positive-semidefinite, its singular value decomposition is identical to its eigenvalue decomposition and Eq. (3.48) can be written as

$$\hat{C}^+ = \hat{Q} \hat{E}^+ \hat{Q}^T \quad (3.48)$$

where Q is the matrix whose column contains the normalized eigenvectors of \hat{C} and E is the diagonal matrix containing the eigenvalues. We carry out the

decomposition of \hat{C} using the Linear Algebra Package (LAPACK) library and compute \hat{C}^+ using Eq. (3.48). After we obtain C_{ij}^+ , we conduct the reconstruction as stated in Section 3.2.1. Note that during this procedure, we have excluded $d_i(1)$ when identifying $m_0(i)$ in step (3) as nodes of degree one are rather uncommon in general networks of interest. This condition can be easily relaxed without significant effect on the overall accuracy except that there would be a few spurious nodes of degree one.

3.4.2 Simulating the weighted networks

Two types of weighted networks have been used to test our method. The first type is a weighted random (WR) network of $N = 100$ nodes which has the topology of a random network with connection probability $p = 0.2$ and the coupling strength g_{ij} is drawn randomly from a Gaussian distribution with mean μ and standard deviation γ . Two different sets of μ and γ are used depending on the intrinsic dynamics being simulated: (i) $\mu = 5, \gamma = 2$ for the consensus dynamics and Rössler dynamics with hyperbolic tangent coupling, and (ii) $\mu = 10, \gamma = 2$ for FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics. The second network is a weighted scale-free (WSF) network [59] which is a generalized version of the BA scale-free network with a power-law node strength distribution $P(s)$ in addition to the power-law degree distribution $P(k)$. We apply the following generative model with the parameters $m = 5$ and $g_0 = 10$:

- (1) Beginning with a small number m_0 of unconnected nodes, add a new node at each step, which connects to $m = m_0$ existing nodes. The probability that a new node j will connect to an existing node i is $p_i = k_i / \sum_q k_q$.
- (2) Each link $i \leftrightarrow j$ of the newly added node j is assigned a coupling strength of $g_{ij} = g_0 k_i / \sum_{\{i'\}} k_{i'}$. Here g_0 is a global coupling strength

factor to adjust the overall strength of the connections, and the sum $\sum_{\{i'\}}$ is over all existing nodes i' connected to the new node j at the time it is added.

For the weighted networks, we have used the following dynamics on the weighted networks in addition to the consensus dynamics: FHN1 dynamics, FHN2 dynamics, and the Rössler dynamics with hyperbolic tangent coupling. In our simulations, we take $\sigma = 1$ and use the Euler-Maruyama solver in most of the cases. For the WSF network with Rössler, FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics, the large network size ($N = 1000$) together with the greater number of equations required to be solved requires a more efficient algorithm. We use the Weak Order 2 Runge-Kutta (RKW2) method [64] for these cases. Please refer to Appendix A for more details on the RKW2 method. The numerical solvers used and the values of Δt for the cases studied are listed in Table 3.1.

Network	Dynamics	Solver	Δt
WR ($\mu = 5, \gamma = 2$)	consensus	Euler-Maruyama	1×10^{-4}
WR ($\mu = 5, \gamma = 2$)	Rössler	Euler-Maruyama	1×10^{-4}
WR ($\mu = 10, \gamma = 2$)	FHN1	Euler-Maruyama	1×10^{-5}
WR ($\mu = 10, \gamma = 2$)	FHN2	Euler-Maruyama	1×10^{-5}
WSF	consensus	Euler-Maruyama	1×10^{-4}
WSF	Rössler	RKW2	5×10^{-4}
WSF	FHN1	RKW2	5×10^{-4}
WSF	FHN2	RKW2	5×10^{-4}

Table 3.1: Numerical solver used and values of Δt in the simulation of combinations of different networks and dynamics.

After solving for $x_i(t)$, the dynamical covariance matrix \hat{C} is found and the pseudoinverse \hat{C}^+ calculated using singular value decomposition similar to what was done for the unweighted networks, and then the algorithm described in Section 3.2.2 is applied to find the connectivity of the network. The

normalized coupling strength and node strength can further be inferred by the procedure stated in Section 3.3. Unless otherwise specified, T_{av} is taken to be 1000.

Chapter 4

Reconstruction of Network

Connectivity: Sensitivity and

Specificity

We first highlight the advantage of our method compared to other existing methods of network reconstruction. Our method has been compared [65] to the standard methods of using the Pearson correlation Π_{ij} and the partial correlation ρ_{ij} as described in Chapter 2. In these methods, a link is identified whenever Π_{ij} or ρ_{ij} exceeds a preset threshold. It has been reported that there is a large amount of overlap between the values of Π_{ij} for connected and unconnected pairs of nodes in a random network with consensus dynamics. This overlap is caused by the interference of indirect paths between nodes discussed in Chapter 2. In fact, it has been shown that the number of errors of the Pearson correlation method significantly exceeds that of our method for the random network and a BA scale-free network with consensus, FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics even when the best possible threshold is set for the former method by choosing the threshold which gives the closest total number of

links to the actual network. As for the partial correlation, it has been shown to give comparable results to our method when the node degree is nearly uniform as in a random network, for which ρ_{ij} would be roughly proportional to r_{ij} . However, when there is a wide distribution of node degree in the network such as in a scale-free network, the performance would be inferior to our method. In the case of the BA scale-free network with consensus dynamics, it has indeed been observed that much more overlap exists in the values of ρ_{ij} belonging to the connected and unconnected nodes than in r_{ij} . In addition, the reconstruction using ρ_{ij} consistently gives more errors than our method for consensus, FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on the BA scale-free network.

In the following sections of this chapter, we present the results of the reconstruction using our method for the different cases studied systematically. The results for unweighted networks and weighted networks will be presented in Sections 4.1 and 4.2 respectively. For each case, we measure the accuracy of the inferred network connectivity $A_{ij}^{(e)}$ using the sensitivity $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and specificity $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ of the individual nodes, which are respectively the percentage of nodes that are correctly inferred to be linked to node i [true positives $n_{\text{tp}}(i)$] and the percentage of nodes that are correctly inferred to be unconnected to node i [true negatives $n_{\text{tn}}(i)$]. In other words,

$$p_{\text{sen}}(i) \equiv \frac{n_{\text{tp}}(i)}{k_i} \times 100\% , \quad p_{\text{spec}}(i) \equiv \frac{n_{\text{tn}}(i)}{N - 1 - k_i} \times 100\% . \quad (4.1)$$

Here we have used the fact that node i contains k_i links in total while $N - 1 - k_i$ nodes are unconnected to it. The overall sensitivity and specificity of the reconstructed connectivity for the entire network can be defined as

$$P_{\text{SEN}} \equiv \frac{N_{\text{TP}}}{\sum_i k_i} \times 100\% , \quad P_{\text{SPEC}} \equiv \frac{N_{\text{TN}}}{\sum_i (N - 1 - k_i)} \times 100\% \quad (4.2)$$

where $N_{\text{TP}} \equiv \sum_i n_{\text{tp}}(i)$ and $N_{\text{TN}} \equiv \sum_i n_{\text{tn}}(i)$. The overall sensitivity P_{SEN} and specificity P_{SPEC} can also be written as weighted averages of the nodal sensitivity $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and specificity $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ respectively:

$$P_{\text{SEN}} = \sum_i p_c(i) p_{\text{sen}}(i), \quad P_{\text{SPEC}} = \sum_i p_u(i) p_{\text{spec}}(i) \quad (4.3)$$

where

$$p_c(i) \equiv \frac{k_i}{\sum_i k_i}, \quad p_u(i) \equiv \frac{N - 1 - k_i}{\sum_i (N - 1 - k_i)}. \quad (4.4)$$

Thus P_{SEN} is more sensitive to nodes with large degree and P_{SPEC} is more sensitive to nodes with small degree.

4.1 Results for unweighted networks

To illustrate the process of finding the separation in the values of r_{ij} , Fig. 4.1 shows $r_i(m)$ as a function of m . A clear separation of the values of $r_i(m)$ is indeed observed and the quality of the separation can be quantified by $\delta(i) = 21.0$. The overall sensitivity P_{SEN} and specificity P_{SPEC} are presented in Table 4.1 for the various cases studied. It shows excellent accuracy of our method with both P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} over 90%. It can also be observed that P_{SPEC} is generally larger than P_{SEN} . Part of the reason is that most of the nodes have degree much smaller than $N/2$ in the networks studied, so for the same number of errors the effect on the percentage of links correctly inferred is larger than that on the percentage of correctly inferred non-existent links. As mentioned in Section 3.4.1, we excluded $d_i(1)$ when finding the separation in r_{ij} such that $m_0(i) \neq 1$. We have also presented P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} obtained without this requirement for two of the cases studied in Table 4.1. The results are identical for the consensus dynamics on random network with or

without this requirement, while relaxing the requirement gives slightly lower P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} for the BA scale-free network with FHN2 dynamics. The difference in the latter is mainly contributed by a small number of nodes with low sensitivity which will be discussed below in more detail.

Figure 4.1: The values of $r_i(m)$ as a function of m for a certain node i of the random network with consensus dynamics and $\sigma = g = 1$.

We then study the nodal sensitivity $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and specificity $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ in detail. Figure 4.2 shows $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ of our method for the random network with consensus, FHN1, FHN2 dynamics. Our method gives near perfect accuracy for consensus, FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics. Our method even provides perfect reconstruction in the case of FHN1. This shows that our method is also applicable to systems with nonlinear intrinsic dynamics. For the random network, we study the additional case of the nonlinear cubic coupling form in Fig. 4.3. This case fares slightly less well than the others, but apart from a node with $p_{\text{sen}}(i) \approx 20\%$ caused by an anomalous gap near the lower end of the $r_i(m)$ values, all other nodes have satisfactory $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ above 80%. In Fig. 4.4 we report $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ for consensus dynamics on the random network obtained without the requirement $m_0(i) \neq 1$ and show that the results of reconstruction is the same for this

Network	N	Dynamics	σ	g	P_{SEN}	P_{SPEC}
random	100	consensus	1	1	99.80	99.95
random	100	consensus	1	1	99.80*	99.95*
random	100	FHN1	1	10	100	100
random	100	FHN2	1	10	99.80	99.37
random	100	cubic coupling	1	1	95.67	96.69
random	100	Kuramoto	1	1	93.15	99.39
random	100	Kuramoto	1	10	98.08	98.99
C. elegans	279	consensus	1	1	99.87	99.98
C. elegans	279	FHN1	1	10	96.28	99.70
C. elegans	279	FHN2	1	10	98.21	99.32
BA scale-free	1000	consensus	1	1	100	99.9996
BA scale-free	1000	FHN1	1	10	97.49	99.998
BA scale-free	1000	FHN2	1	10	96.69	99.999
BA scale-free	1000	FHN2	1	10	96.39*	99.996*

Table 4.1: Overall sensitivity and specificity of the method for the different unweighted networks and dynamics. Results with the superscript * are obtained without the requirement of $m_0(i) \neq 1$.

case. We proceed to the case of Kuramoto model on random network with $\sigma = g = 1$ in Fig. 4.5. Our method still shows a reasonably high accuracy for the majority of the nodes, suggesting that our method may be applicable even when the intrinsic dynamics is not entirely identical. However, we see an outlying node with a very small $p_{sen}(i)$ of 5% (labeled by closed circle). We then find that this node ($i = 8$) has a very high natural frequency ω_i as presented in Fig. 4.6. As mentioned in Chapter 1, the oscillators with natural frequencies far from the mean do not readily synchronize with others. This is apparent in the time series shown in Fig. 4.7 for the node $i = 8$ and three other nodes with more typical values of ω_i . It can be seen that the activity of the node $i = 8$ is quite distinct from the other nodes which have much closer phases. This outlying behavior correlates with the poor sensitivity we see in the reconstruction. On the other hand, Fig. 4.8 shows that the accuracy for this node can be improved by increasing the coupling strength

to $g = 10$ such that there is more synchronization. The increase in the level of synchronization is reflected by the average phase coherence $\langle R \rangle_{T_{av}}$ that goes from 0.928 for $g = 1$ to 0.986 when $g = 10$, and is also evident in the time series shown in Fig. 4.9. The requirement of a relatively high level of synchronization for successful reconstruction may seem counterintuitive at first because no information on the connectivity can be obtained from the dynamics if every node is perfectly synchronized. However, the presence of noise perturbs the network and prevents it from being perfectly synchronized. In addition, a high level of synchronization makes the relation between the dynamical covariance and network connectivity more accurate as the effects of other factors such as difference in intrinsic dynamics are minimized. Thus for our method a high level of synchronization is desirable as long as there is a reasonable amount of noise.

Plots of $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ for the C. elegans neuronal network and BA scale-free network are presented in Figs. 4.10 and 4.11 respectively. In general, the accuracy of our method for the C. elegans neuronal network and BA scale-free network are worse than the random network with the same dynamics. It is to be expected as these networks have nontrivial structures which do not exist in a random network. Nonetheless, $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ is still over 70% in these two networks for the majority of the nodes with FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics. In Fig. 4.12, we show also results for the FHN2 dynamics with BA scale-free network obtained without the requirement $m_0(i) \neq 1$ that restricts the reconstructed node degree to be larger than 1. The results are similar to previously except a few nodes with low $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ of 50%. These result from a small number of nodes with $k_i = 2$ being mistakenly inferred to be $k_i^{(e)} = 1$.

We proceed to discuss the dependence of the nodal accuracies on the node degree k_i . We focus on the cases of FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on BA scale-

Figure 4.2: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for random network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\sigma = g = 1$), (b) FHN1 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$), and (c) FHN2 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$).

Figure 4.3: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for random network with the cubic coupling form $h(x_i, x_j) = (x_j - x_i)^3$ ($\sigma = g = 1$).

Figure 4.4: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for random network with consensus dynamics using $\sigma = g = 1$ without the requirement of $m_0(i) \neq 1$.

Figure 4.5: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for random network with the Kuramoto model using $\sigma = g = 1$. We label the particularly low $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ of the node $i = 8$ with a closed circle.

Figure 4.6: The values of ω_i used in the simulation, which is drawn from a Lorentz distribution. The node $i = 8$ which has a very low $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ is labeled with a closed circle.

Figure 4.7: The time series $\theta_i(t)$ of the Kuramoto model on the random network for the node $i = 8$ (black) and three other nodes with more typical ω_i (red, blue and green).

Figure 4.8: Same as Fig. 4.5 but with a larger coupling strength $g = 10$. Note that $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ of the node $i = 8$ (closed circle) shows marked improvement over the case with smaller $g = 1$.

Figure 4.9: Same as Fig. 4.7 but with a larger coupling strength $g = 10$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4.10: Same as Fig. 4.2 for the *C. Elegans* neuronal network.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4.11: Same as Fig. 4.2 for the BA scale-free network.

Figure 4.12: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for BA scale-free network with FHN2 dynamics using $\sigma = g = 1$ without the requirement of $m_0(i) \neq 1$.

free network, as this network contains hubs and therefore has a wide range of k_i . Equation (3.32) would suggest that the quality of separation $\delta(i) \sim 1/k_i$. In Figs. 4.13 and 4.14 for BA scale-free network with FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics respectively, we see indeed $\delta(i)$ goes roughly as $1/k_i$, meaning that the separation deteriorates as k_i increases. We expect the number of errors would increase when $\delta(i)$ decreases and the separation becomes worse. We look at the number of false negatives $n_{\text{fn}}(i) = k_i - n_{\text{tp}}(i)$ for each node in Figs. 4.15 and 4.16. The number of errors increases with k_i and verifies our expectation.

Next we further investigate how the performance of our method depends on the parameters σ and g . As an example, we focus on the case of consensus dynamics on random network. Our method gives satisfactory reconstruction for a wide range of σ and g provided that both are sufficiently large. More specifically, our method can achieve perfect reconstruction ($P_{\text{SEN}} = P_{\text{SPEC}} = 100\%$) when $\sigma \geq 0.1$ and $g \geq 10$. To facilitate visualization of the performance of our method, we draw an arbitrary threshold at 95% and denote the network reconstruction as satisfactory if both P_{SEN} and

Figure 4.13: The measure of quality of separation $\delta(i)$ for node i against node degree k_i on the BA scale-free network with FHN1 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$). The red solid line is proportional to $1/k_i$ and is for guiding the eye.

Figure 4.14: Same as Fig. 4.13 but for FHN2 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$) on BA scale-free network. The red solid line is proportional to $1/k_i$ and is for guiding the eye.

P_{SPEC} exceeds 95% and unsatisfactory otherwise. We probe the parameter space and presents the "phase" diagram of the performance of our method in Fig. 4.17. Note that the transition from unsatisfactory to satisfactory reconstruction is a smooth crossover rather than an actual sharp phase transition. The result indicates that our method works well when σ and g are both greater than some threshold. In addition, the threshold value of σ decreases when g is increased. The unsatisfactory performance when g is insufficiently large can be understood by recalling the approximations made when deriving the relation in Eq. (3.30) between network connectivity and dynamical covariance. In the derivation, the terms that vanish in the limit of time $t \rightarrow \infty$ contain the factors $e^{-g(\lambda_k + \lambda_{k'})t}$ and $e^{-2g\lambda_k t}$ in Eqs. (3.23) and (3.24) respectively. Thus a smaller g would require a longer averaging time T_{av} in order for those terms to vanish and Eq. (3.30) to hold. Equivalently, at a fixed T_{av} , decreasing g would lead to a lower performance of the network inference. These two features are validated in Table 4.2 where we vary the parameters σ , g and T_{av} . When g is decreased it leads to lower P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} , while the performance can be improved by using a longer T_{av} . Moreover, we found that the parameter Δ as defined in Eq. (3.34) indeed gives good prediction for the reconstruction performance: when Δ is sufficiently large, P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} are both close to 100%.

σ	g	T_{ave}	P_{SEN}	P_{SPEC}	Δ
0.01	0.1	1000	49.4	96.2	2.7
0.01	1	1000	87.7	98.0	7.1
0.01	10	1000	91.0	98.8	18.0
0.01	100	1000	97.7	99.3	30.1
0.1	0.1	1000	59.5	96.5	2.6
0.1	1	1000	99.6	99.7	17.1
0.1	10	1000	100.0	100.0	47.6
0.1	100	1000	100.0	100.0	72.6
1	0.1	1000	52.3	96.7	2.9
1	1	1000	99.8	99.95	22.2
1	10	1000	100.0	100.0	66.6
1	100	1000	100.0	100.0	80.4
1	0.1	10000	99.9	99.9	21.3
1	1	10000	100.0	100.0	67.1
10	0.1	1000	58.1	96.3	2.6
10	1	1000	99.7	99.9	22.1
10	10	1000	100.0	100.0	65.3
10	100	1000	100.0	100.0	80.4
100	0.1	1000	58.2	96.3	2.6
100	1	1000	99.7	99.9	22.1
100	10	1000	100.0	100.0	65.3
100	100	1000	100.0	100.0	80.4

Table 4.2: Dependence of P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} on the parameters σ , g and T_{av} for the random network with consensus dynamics.

Figure 4.17: Phase diagram showing how the performance of our method depends on the parameters σ and g for the random network with consensus dynamics and $T_{ave} = 1000$. Satisfactory results (both P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} greater than 95%) are represented by open circles and unsatisfactory results by closed circles.

4.2 Results for weighted networks

Before we discuss the results of reconstructing the network connectivity of the weighted networks, we demonstrate the algorithm generalized for weighted networks by applying it to the simple case of the unweighted random network with consensus dynamics. The overall sensitivity P_{SEN} and specificity P_{SPEC} of the reconstruction of the networks are shown in Table 4.3. Compared to the case of using the algorithm designed for unweighted networks, P_{SEN} resulting from the use of the generalized algorithm on the random network with consensus dynamics is slightly higher while that of P_{SPEC} is slightly lower. This is because the algorithm for weighted networks has a more lenient criterion for a separation in r_{ij} , leading to more links being identified but also with more false positives. Both increasing the coupling strength g and lengthening the averaging time T_{av} improve the reconstruction and can lead to perfect reconstruction of the connectivity. The nodal accuracies $p_{sen}(i)$ and

$p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ for the case of random network with consensus dynamics, $\sigma = g = 1$ and $T_{av} = 1000$ are plotted in Fig. 4.18 indicating the reconstruction is very accurate. Since we are considering an unweighted network, the normalized coupling strength $G_{ij} = 1$ for all connections $i - j$. Thus the distribution $P(G)$ of the actual G_{ij} would be a Dirac delta function located at $G = 1$. The distribution inferred using $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ as defined in Eq. (3.36), on the other hand, would not be exact and shows a spread around $G = 1$ which is well approximated by a Gaussian distribution (Fig. 4.19) centered at 1. The error in $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ is therefore given by the standard deviation of the fitted Gaussian distribution, which has a value of about 0.138. The values of $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ become more accurate with less spread when a larger coupling strength $g = 10$ is used (Fig. 4.20) or when longer averaging times $T_{av} = 2000$ and 10000 are used (Fig. 4.21). The improved accuracy is evident from the smaller errors given by the standard deviations of 0.0442 for $g = 10$ and 0.0461 for $T_{av} = 10000$. Note that an averaging time of $T_{av} = 2000$ already gives perfect reconstruction of the network connectivity ($P_{\text{SEN}} = P_{\text{SPEC}} = 100\%$), but has a larger error in $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ than the case with $T_{av} = 10000$. This indicates that the improvement in $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ is not only due to improvement in reconstructing the network topology as measured by P_{SEN} and P_{SPEC} , but is also related to the actual magnitude of the terms C_{ij}^+ as appears in Eq. (3.36) when calculating $G_{ij}^{(e)}$.

Next we progress to discuss the results on weighted networks in Table 4.3. Here we focus on the reconstruction of network connectivity, and the reconstruction of weights will be discussed in Chapter 5. Similar to the case of unweighted networks, the weighted scale-free (WSF) network with scale-free properties tends to be more difficult to reconstruct than the weighted random (WR) network without nontrivial structure, and this is especially

true for the FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics. This is partly caused by a large disparity of the values of g_{ij} for some nodes i which dominates all the other links in the same node, leading to low sensitivity. These nodes are created when a new node i is added at the later stage of the network growth process of the WSF network and links to an existing hub h that has a high degree. As node i is added at a later stage of network growth, it tends to have a small degree in the final network generated. Furthermore, the coupling strength g_{ih} between this node and the existing hub will be extremely large, since the coupling strength is proportional to the degree of the existing node. As the number of hubs in the network is small, most other connections in node i will be linked to nodes with much smaller degree. As a result, all these connections would be much weaker than the one between node i and h . The wide distribution of coupling strength together with the small degree of node i would then cause a large disparity in the values of g_{ij} .

This large disparity in g_{ij} will then interfere with our algorithm of finding the separation in r_{ij} by causing some exceptionally large values of the difference $d_i(m)$ that dominates the mean $\langle d_i \rangle$ and standard deviation ζ_i . This in turn affects the threshold $\langle d_i \rangle + 2\zeta_i$ for identifying a separation by making it too large to pick up any separation other than the exceptionally large differences. This implies that in these cases we can improve the accuracy of our method by not including these exceptionally large differences when calculating the mean and standard deviation of $d_i(m)$. The exceptionally large differences can be identified by the following analysis. Consider N numbers with mean M and standard deviation S . Let $x = M + \lambda S$ be one of these numbers. Denote the mean and standard deviation of the remaining numbers

when x is removed by \tilde{M} and \tilde{S} respectively. We have

$$\tilde{M} = \frac{MN - x}{N - 1} = M - \frac{\lambda}{N - 1}S \quad (4.5)$$

$$\tilde{S}^2 = \frac{(S^2 + M^2)N - x^2}{N - 1} - \tilde{M}^2 \Rightarrow \tilde{S} = S\sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{N - 1}}\sqrt{1 - \frac{\lambda^2}{N - 1}} \quad (4.6)$$

Thus when λ is of $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{N})$, \tilde{S} would be significantly smaller than S and such a value x would significantly raise the threshold of separation $M + 2S$. Therefore we can eliminate the adverse effect of the very large differences by not using the values of $d_i(m)$ with $\lambda > K\sqrt{N}$ (K is a constant of order 1) when computing the mean and standard deviation. We set $K = 0.85$. In other words, it means using the following criterion to identify the separations:

$$d_i(m) > \langle \tilde{d}_i \rangle + 2\tilde{\mu}_i \quad (4.7)$$

where $\langle \tilde{d}_i \rangle$ and $\tilde{\mu}_i$ denote respectively the mean and standard deviation of $d_i(m)$ calculated using only those values of $d_i(m) \leq \langle d_i \rangle + K\sqrt{N}\zeta_i$.

The results of applying this improvement to our method is also presented in Table 4.3 for FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on WSF network. A significant improvement in P_{SEN} is observed. Moreover, akin to the case of unweighted networks, increasing the averaging time T_{av} can also improve the accuracy dramatically.

Next we look into the nodal sensitivity $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and specificity $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ of our method for the weighted networks. The results are shown in Fig. 4.22 for the WR network and in Fig. 4.23 for the WSF network respectively with the different dynamics studied. In general, reconstruction of the connectivity of weighted networks gives lower accuracy than their unweighted counterparts. Nevertheless, our method gives satisfactory results for the WR network with

Network	Dynamics	T_{av}	$P_{SEN}(\%)$	$P_{SPEC}(\%)$
random ($\sigma = g = 1$)	consensus	1000	100.0	99.82
random ($\sigma = 1, g = 10$)	consensus	1000	100.0	100.00
random ($\sigma = 1, g = 1$)	consensus	2000	100.0	100.00
random ($\sigma = 1, g = 1$)	consensus	10000	100.0	100.00
WR ($\mu = 5, \gamma = 2$)	consensus	1000	94.3	100.00
WR ($\mu = 5, \gamma = 2$)	Rössler	1000	94.2	100.00
WR ($\mu = 10, \gamma = 2$)	FHN1	1000	99.5	100.00
WR ($\mu = 10, \gamma = 2$)	FHN2	1000	98.1	99.97
WSF	consensus	1000	88.3	99.98
WSF	Rössler	1000	86.0	99.99
WSF	FHN1	1000	56.8	99.83
WSF	FHN1	1000	63.5*	99.56*
WSF	FHN1	5000	85.5	99.87
WSF	FHN2	1000	61.4	99.80
WSF	FHN2	1000	67.8*	99.58*
WSF	FHN2	5000	85.7	99.86

Table 4.3: Overall sensitivity P_{SEN} and specificity P_{SPEC} for the unweighted random network with consensus dynamics and the weighted networks with different dynamics. The superscript * denotes results obtained using the criterion for identifying a separation given in Eq. (4.7) instead.

$p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ higher than 80% for nearly all the nodes in all the different dynamics tested. On the other hand, the accuracy for the WSF network tends to be poorer as discussed earlier. In Fig. 4.23, we see that nodes corresponding to small i have better sensitivity. This is because the hubs usually has small i , as those are the nodes that are added early on in the network growth process and are more likely to develop into hubs. Since hubs have much higher degree than other nodes, they will have better sensitivity for the same number of errors in the reconstruction as the percentage of links correctly inferred is higher. We further study in more detail the effect of using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when finding the separation in the values of r_{ij} . In Fig. 4.24, we focus on the WSF network with FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics and observe that the exclusion of exceptionally large differences in determining the threshold for identifying a separation primarily improves the smallest values of $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$. This is due to the fact that the nodes with a large disparity in g_{ij} usually has a severely underestimated number of links and therefore a very low sensitivity. By remedying the effect of this disparity, the accuracy for these nodes with extremely low $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ can be improved. On the other hand, lengthening the averaging time improves the accuracy for all the nodes simultaneously as in Fig. 4.25 for FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on WSF network.

The accuracy of inferring the connectivity of a node naturally depends on the properties of that particular node. In Eq. (3.31), the separation between the connected and unconnected values of r_{ij} is given by $(\min_j g_{ij})/s_i$ where $(\min_j g_{ij})$ denotes the minimum of g_{ij} at a fixed i and we expect that the accuracy of reconstruction would increase with $(\min_j g_{ij})/s_i$. To check this, we take the cases of WSF network with Rössler and FHN1 dynamics as examples and plot the number of false negatives $n_{fn}(i)$ and false positives

Figure 4.18: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for the random network (unweighted) with consensus dynamics, $\sigma = g = 1$ and $T_{av} = 1000$ obtained using the generalized algorithm for weighted networks.

Figure 4.19: The distribution of the normalized coupling strength $P(G)$ inferred using $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ (circles) for the random network with consensus dynamics, $\sigma = g = 1$ and $T_{av} = 1000$. Solid line is a fit of the Gaussian distribution with mean 1 and standard deviation 0.138.

Figure 4.20: Same as Fig. 4.19 but with $\sigma = 1$, $g = 10$ and $T_{av} = 1000$. Solid line is a fit of the Gaussian distribution with mean 1 and standard deviation 0.0442.

Figure 4.21: Same as Fig. 4.19 but with $T_{av} = 2000$ (squares) and 10000 (circles) while $\sigma = g = 1$ remains unchanged. Solid line is a fit of the Gaussian distribution with mean 1 and standard deviation 0.0461. Both $T_{av} = 2000$ and 10000 give perfect reconstruction of the network topology with $P_{SEN} = P_{SPEC} = 100\%$.

Figure 4.22: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for weighted random (WR) network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (b) Rössler dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (c) FHN1 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$), and (d) FHN2 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$).

Figure 4.23: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics.

Figure 4.24: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) obtained by using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when identifying the separation in the values of r_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics.

Figure 4.25: $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ (circles) and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ (triangles) obtained by using a longer averaging time $T_{av} = 5000$ for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 and (b) FHN2 dynamics.

$n_{fn}(i)$ for each node i as a function of $(\min_j g_{ij})/s_i$ in Figs. 4.26 and 4.27 respectively. Indeed, a larger value of $(\min_j g_{ij})/s_i$ is conducive to lower values of both $n_{fn}(i)$ and $n_{fp}(i)$.

Figure 4.26: The number of false negatives $n_{fn}(i)$ when inferring the links of each node i against $(\min_j g_{ij})/s_i$ for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) Rössler dynamics and (b) FHN1 dynamics.

Figure 4.27: The number of false positives $n_{fp}(i)$ when inferring the links of each node i against $(\min_j g_{ij})/s_i$ for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) Rössler dynamics and (b) FHN1 dynamics.

Chapter 5

Reconstruction of Normalized Coupling Strength and Node Strength

In this chapter we present results of the reconstruction of the normalized coupling strength G_{ij} and node strength S_i using the method described in Section 3.3 which culminates in the estimates $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ and $S_i^{(e)}$ in Eq. (3.36). We first check the validity of the approximation $-(\sigma^2/2)C_{ij}^+ \approx g_{ij}$ in Eq. (3.29). We plot $-(\sigma^2/2)C_{ij}^+$ against g_{ij} in Figs. 5.1 and 5.2 for the weighted random (WR) network and weighted scale-free (WSF) network respectively. As seen from the figures, the data points scatter around the line $y = x$ and Eq. (3.29) gives a good approximation for all the cases studied except for the WR network with FHN2 dynamics and WSF network with FHN1 as well as FHN2 dynamics. The scattering is most severe at $g_{ij} = 0$ leading to false positives in inferring the network connectivity, but the amount of scatter can be reduced by increasing T_{av} . For the three cases that exhibits large deviations from Eq. (3.29), we found that they can be described by the

generalized form:

$$-(\sigma^2/2)C_{ij}^+ \approx Bg_{ij} \quad (5.1)$$

with $B > 1$. Those cases also show more scattering, but again the scatter can be improved by increasing T_{av} as in Fig. 5.3, which clearly shows that for these cases the relation converges to a value of $B > 1$. On the other hand, B converges to 1 when the coupling strength is increased. Note that Eq. (3.31) still holds for $B \neq 1$ as that factor would be canceled out when calculating the ratio r_{ij} , so our method would still be applicable.

Figure 5.1: $-(\sigma^2/2)C_{ij}^+$ versus g_{ij} for weighted random (WR) network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (b) Rössler dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (c) FHN1 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$), and (d) FHN2 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$). Dashed line is $y = x$.

Figure 5.2: $-(\sigma^2/2)C_{ij}^+$ versus g_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics.

Figure 5.3: $-(\sigma^2/2)C_{ij}^+$ obtained using $T_{av} = 5000$ versus g_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics.

We then compare the inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ with the actual values G_{ij} in Figs. 5.4 and 5.5 for WR network and WSF network respectively. The reconstruction of normalized coupling strength is satisfactory for all the cases tested on the WR network, albeit with a larger amount of scattering for FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics. For the WSF network, there is clear underestimation of G_{ij} . This is expected as the false negatives (links that fail to be detected) correspond to links with relatively small g_{ij} , so the links that did get detected tend to have a large coupling strength and this bias would cause $\langle g \rangle$ to be overestimated, leading to an underestimation of G_{ij} . This underestimation is most apparent for the FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics where a high level of scattering is also observed. Nevertheless, these cases are well approximated by

$$G_{ij}^{(e)} \approx DG_{ij} \quad (5.2)$$

with D less than but near 1. We focus on FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics and found that D becomes closer to 1 when the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) is used instead when identifying the separation in r_{ij} during the reconstruction (Fig. 5.6) or when the averaging time T_{av} is lengthened (Fig. 5.7), as presented in Table 5.1. The former improves $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ by remedying the underestimation of k_i due to the large disparity of g_{ij} in some nodes of the WSF network while the latter lead to a better reconstruction in general by improving the approximation in Eq. (5.1). We further study the accuracy of $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ quantitatively by calculating the average percentage error of $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ defined as:

$$\xi \equiv \frac{1}{\sum_i k_i^{(e)}} \sum_{n,l \leftrightarrow n} \left| \frac{G_{nl}^{(e)} - G_{nl}}{G_{nl}} \right| \times 100\% \quad (5.3)$$

where the subscript $l \leftrightarrow n$ denotes a sum over nodes l that are inferred to

be connected to node n . The values of ξ are reported in Table 5.2 and are consistent with the trends discussed earlier. In particular, the errors for the WR network are relatively low with all values of ξ below or around 10%, and the same goes for the WSF network with consensus and Rössler dynamics. The errors are the largest at around 30% for FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on the WSF network. The percentage error is improved only marginally for these two cases when the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) is used to identify the separation in r_{ij} , but significant improvement can be obtained by increasing the averaging time T_{av} .

Dynamics	T_{av}	D	D'
FHN1	1000	0.753	0.826
FHN1	1000	0.920*	0.983*
FHN1	5000	0.926	0.907
FHN2	1000	0.776	0.822
FHN2	1000	0.906*	0.933*
FHN2	5000	0.920	0.893

Table 5.1: The values of the fitting parameters D and D' for WSF network with FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics. The superscript * denotes results obtained using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when finding the separation in the values of r_{ij} .

Figure 5.4: The inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ against the actual values G_{ij} for weighted random (WR) network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (b) Rössler dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (c) FHN1 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$), and (d) FHN2 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$). The false negatives are labeled in red and the false positives in blue.

Figure 5.5: The inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ against the actual values G_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics. Solid line is fit of the form $y = Dx$.

Figure 5.6: The inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ obtained by using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when identifying the separation in r_{ij} , against the actual values G_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics. Solid line is fit of the form $y = Dx$.

Figure 5.7: The inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ obtained using $T_{av} = 5000$ against the actual values G_{ij} for weighted scale-free (WSF) network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics. Solid line is fit of the form $y = Dx$.

Network	Dynamics	T_{av}	$\xi(\%)$
WR ($\mu = 5, \gamma = 2$)	consensus	1000	6.67
WR ($\mu = 5, \gamma = 2$)	Rössler	1000	6.86
WR ($\mu = 10, \gamma = 2$)	FHN1	1000	8.04
WR ($\mu = 10, \gamma = 2$)	FHN2	1000	10.92
WSF	consensus	1000	9.61
WSF	Rössler	1000	11.04
WSF	FHN1	1000	31.21
WSF	FHN1	1000	30.65*
WSF	FHN1	5000	20.70
WSF	FHN2	1000	28.49
WSF	FHN2	1000	28.37*
WSF	FHN2	5000	17.98

Table 5.2: The average percentage error ξ of $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ for the weighted networks with different dynamics. The superscript * denotes results obtained using the criterion for identifying a separation given in Eq. (4.7) instead.

Finally, we look at reconstruction of the normalized node strength S_i . As seen in the comparison of $S_i^{(e)}$ with S_i in Figs. 5.8 and 5.9 for the WR network and WSF network respectively, our method yields excellent accuracy for all cases except FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on WSF network where there is considerable overestimation of S_i . To understand this discrepancy, first consider the normalized coupling strength G_{ij} averaged over a certain node i :

$$\langle G \rangle_i \equiv \frac{\sum_j G_{ij} A_{ij}}{k_i}. \quad (5.4)$$

Then from Eq. (3.35), we have

$$S_i = \left(\frac{k_i}{\langle k \rangle} \right) \langle G \rangle_i. \quad (5.5)$$

Similarly, the inferred average normalized coupling strength of node i is given

by $\langle G \rangle_i^{(e)} \equiv \sum_j G_{ij}^{(e)} A_{ij}^{(e)} / k_i^{(e)}$ and Eq. (5.2) would suggest that

$$\langle G \rangle_i^{(e)} \approx D' \langle G \rangle_i \quad (5.6)$$

where $D' \approx D$. We compare $\langle G \rangle_i^{(e)}$ to $\langle G \rangle_i$ in Fig. 5.10 and obtain the values of D' by fitting $y = D'x$. We observe that for $\langle G \rangle_i \leq 1$ there is much scatter in the data so we only fit the data points with $\langle G \rangle_i > 1$. The reason is that nodes with small $\langle G \rangle_i$ are dominated by weak links that are hard to detect. This is further confirmed by the low $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ for nodes with small $\langle G \rangle_i$ as is evident in Fig. 5.11. The values of D' are reported in Table 5.1. Indeed the value of D' is close to that of D for the same case with a percentage difference below 10%. We eventually derive an estimate for $S_i^{(e)}$:

$$S_i^{(e)} = \left(\frac{k_i^{(e)}}{\langle k \rangle^{(e)}} \right) \langle G \rangle_i^{(e)} \approx D' S_i \frac{(k_i^{(e)} / \langle k \rangle^{(e)})}{(k_i / \langle k \rangle)}. \quad (5.7)$$

In Fig. 5.9 we include this estimate for FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on the WSF network and see that it reproduces the trend of $S_i^{(e)}$ well, meaning that the deviation of $S_i^{(e)}$ from S_i in these cases is due to a discrepancy between $k_i^{(e)}$ and k_i . The latter is further caused by the less satisfactory approximation of Eq. (5.2) for the WSF network with FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics in addition to the underestimation of k_i for nodes with small degree, as they have high disparity of the coupling strength mentioned earlier.

Figure 5.8: The inferred normalized node strength $S_i^{(e)}$ (circles) against the actual values S_i for WR network with (a) consensus dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (b) Rössler dynamics ($\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$), (c) FHN1 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$), and (d) FHN2 dynamics ($\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$).

Figure 5.9: The inferred normalized node strength $S_i^{(e)}$ (circles) against the actual values S_i for WSF network with (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics. In (c) and (d), we show also the estimate $D'S_i(k_i^{(e)}/\langle k \rangle^{(e)})/(k_i/\langle k \rangle)$ for $S_i^{(e)}$ (triangles).

Figure 5.10: The inferred average normalized coupling strength of the i -th node $\langle G \rangle_i^{(e)}$ against the actual values $\langle G \rangle_i$ for WSF network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics. Solid line is the fit $y = D'x$.

Figure 5.11: The nodal sensitivity $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ against $\langle G \rangle_i$ for WSF network with (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics

Chapter 6

Reconstruction of Global Network Properties: Eigenvalue Spectrum, Degree and Strength Distribution

So far we have evaluated the accuracy of our method using measures of local information such as $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ defined at each node or the comparison of the actual and inferred G_{ij} defined for each link. In this chapter we shall study whether our method can accurately reconstruct the global features of a network. The global properties of networks are useful in characterizing different types of networks and predicting their behavior. For example, scale-free networks are characterized by the power-law degree distribution $P(k) \sim k^{-\beta}$ and small-world networks have a high level of clustering together with small average path length as mentioned in Chapter 1. We first study the unweighted networks in Section 6.1, where we reproduce the power-law degree distribution of the BA scale-free network using the inferred

degree $k_i^{(e)}$. We also compare the inferred and actual eigenvalue spectrum $\rho(\lambda)$, which is defined as the probability density function of the eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix. After that we proceed to the weighted networks in Section 6.2 and present the reconstruction of the distribution of the normalized coupling strength $P(G)$. Furthermore, since the WSF network has power-law distributions for the node strength distribution in addition to the degree distribution, we investigate also the reconstruction of the distribution of normalized node strength $P(S)$.

6.1 Results for unweighted networks

The inferred degree distribution is obtained by computing the probability density of the inferred degree $k_i^{(e)}$. The fractional error of the latter is related to the nodal sensitivity $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and specificity $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ by:

$$\frac{k_i^{(e)}}{k_i} - 1 = \left(\frac{N-1}{k_i} - 1 \right) \left[1 - \frac{\text{spec}(i)}{100\%} \right] - \left[1 - \frac{\text{sen}(i)}{100\%} \right]. \quad (6.1)$$

This implies that the fractional error would be more significant for nodes with small k_i for the same $p_{\text{sen}}(i)$ and $p_{\text{spec}}(i)$ so it would generally be more difficult to infer k_i accurately for such nodes. Comparison of the actual and inferred degree distribution of the BA scale-free network is presented in Fig. 6.1 for the consensus, FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics. Our method reproduces very well the power-law region of the distribution for all the different dynamics tested. Note that the large amount of scatter of the data points in the regime of large k for both the actual and inferred distribution is due to the small number of hubs in the BA scale-free network causing insufficient statistics. The range of the power law can be increased by using a larger network size N .

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6.1: Comparison of the actual degree distribution $P(k)$ of the BA scale-free network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) consensus dynamics ($\sigma = g = 1$), (b) FHN1 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$), and (c) FHN2 dynamics ($\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$).

Next we move on to reconstruct the eigenvalue spectrum of the adjacency matrix of the networks. The eigenvalue spectrum conveys significant information about the structure and dynamical behavior of a network. For example, the eigenvalues with small values have been shown to be contributed by weakly connected nodes that have small degree [66]. On the other side of the spectrum, the largest eigenvalue determines the threshold of infection rate above which an epidemic will spread on a network [67, 68]. It also controls the critical coupling K_c of the Kuramoto phase oscillators (please refer to Chapter 1) for the onset of synchronization on an arbitrary network [69]. For the random network there exists an analytical expression for the eigenvalue spectrum in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ known as the Wigner semicircle distribution [70–72]:

$$\rho(\lambda) = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{\pi R^2} \sqrt{R^2 - \lambda^2}, & |\lambda| < R, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (6.2)$$

where $R^2 = 4Np(1-p)$ and there is exactly one large eigenvalue with a value of pN separated from the bulk distribution. For the eigenvalue spectrum of the BA scale-free network, such a simple analytical expression is not available and its spectrum has been determined numerically [73, 74]. The spectrum is found to be very different from the semicircle distribution, with a much more prominent central peak that decays exponentially near the center and long tails that decays as a power law. Interestingly, the exponent of the tail of the spectrum is found to be related to the exponent β of the degree distribution such that $\rho(\lambda) \sim |\lambda|^{1-2\beta}$. In Figs. 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4, we found excellent agreement between the actual eigenvalue spectrum and the spectrum inferred using $A_{ij}^{(e)}$ for the random network, the C. elegans network and the BA scale-free network respectively. We also check that the actual eigenvalue

spectrum of the random network and BA scale-free network matches that of the semicircle distribution and the numerical results from Ref. [74] respectively. Note that for the random network, the bulk of the spectrum is close to the semicircle distribution and the largest eigenvalue is near $pN = 20$. For the BA scale-free network, we show also the case with a small $g = 0.1$ that gives unsatisfactory reconstruction. We observe that for this case the height of the central peak is underestimated while the intermediate region is overestimated and the tail does not show the characteristic power-law decay.

Figure 6.2: Comparison of the actual eigenvalue spectrum $\rho(\lambda)$ of the random network (circles) with the inferred spectrum using consensus dynamics with $\sigma = g = 1$ (squares), FHN1 dynamics with $\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$ (triangles), and FHN2 dynamics with $\sigma = 1$ and $g = 10$ (diamonds). Solid line is the Wigner semicircle distribution for the actual spectrum in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Figure 6.3: Comparison of the actual eigenvalue spectrum $\rho(\lambda)$ of the *C. elegans* neuronal network with the inferred spectrum. The symbols are the same as in Fig. 6.2.

Figure 6.4: Comparison of the actual eigenvalue spectrum $\rho(\lambda)$ of the BA scale-free network with the inferred spectrum. The symbols are the same as in Fig. 6.2. Solid line is the numerical result from Ref. [74] for the spectrum of BA scale-free network with $N = 5000$ and $m = 2$ averaged over 40 realizations. Dashed line is the inferred spectrum obtained using consensus dynamics with $\sigma = 1$ and a small $g = 0.1$ which is not sufficient to give an accurate reconstruction at $T_{av} = 1000$.

6.2 Results for weighted networks

For weighted networks, we are also interested in global features of the network related to the coupling strength of the links. A natural first step would be to study the reconstruction of the distribution $P(G)$ of the normalized coupling strength G_{ij} . We compare the actual distribution $P(G)$ with that obtained from the inferred normalized coupling strength $G_{ij}^{(e)}$ in Figs. 6.5 and 6.6 for the WR network and WSF network respectively. We observe that some links with small G_{ij} are missing as it is more difficult to detect very weak connections, but otherwise the overall trend of the distribution is reproduced faithfully. For the cases of WSF network with FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics, we also see that there is marked overestimation of the peak of the distribution. The poorer accuracy of these two cases is consistent with the results reported in Chapter 5. We include the result for FHN2 dynamics on the WSF network with a longer averaging time $T_{av} = 5000$ in Fig. 6.6 and confirm that the deviation from the actual $P(G)$ can be remedied by averaging over a longer duration.

Figure 6.5: Comparison of the actual normalized coupling strength distribution $P(G)$ of the WR network (solid lines) with the inferred distribution using consensus (circles) and Rössler (triangles) dynamics with $\mu = 5$ and $\gamma = 2$ as well as FHN1 (squares) and FHN2 (diamonds) dynamics with $\mu = 10$ and $\gamma = 2$. An averaging time of $T_{av} = 1000$ is used.

Figure 6.6: Comparison of the actual normalized coupling strength distribution $P(G)$ of the WSF network (solid line) with the inferred distribution using consensus (circles), Rössler (triangles), FHN1 (squares) and FHN2 (diamonds) dynamics. An averaging time of $T_{av} = 1000$ is used for the symbols while the dashed line is the result for FHN2 dynamics with $T_{av} = 5000$.

From this point on, we concentrate on the WSF network and investigate the reconstruction of its power-law degree and node strength distribution. The topology of the WSF network is basically that of a BA scale-free network so the degree distribution $P(k)$ would have the same properties. However, the non-uniformity of the coupling strength of the links makes it harder to infer the connections accurately and we would expect more errors. We carry out a comparison of the actual $P(k)$ and that inferred using $k_i^{(e)}$ for the WSF network in Fig. 6.7. We see that in the inferred distribution there are nodes with very small k_i that does not exist in the actual network. This is partly caused by the issue of low sensitivity of the nodes with small k_i due to the large disparity of g_{ij} discussed in Section 4.2. Despite this discrepancy, our method captures the power-law region of $P(k)$ using the consensus and Rössler dynamics with high accuracy. For the FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics, there is some underestimation of the density from small to intermediate k , but nonetheless the power-law behavior is preserved. This underestimation is related to the existence of the erroneously inferred nodes with very small degree. As the density is normalized, overestimation of the density at the small- k regime would lead to underestimation elsewhere. In Fig. 6.8, we further demonstrate that the overestimation of density at small k and the underestimation at intermediate k can be improved by using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when finding the separation in the values of r_{ij} during the reconstruction. There we can see that the density of nodes with very small degree is decreased, and the underestimation is eliminated at the intermediate range of k . We also show that the reconstruction of $P(k)$ can be improved by increasing the averaging time T_{av} in Fig. 6.9 using the FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics as examples.

Figure 6.7: Comparison of the actual degree distribution $P(k)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics.

Figure 6.8: Comparison of the actual degree distribution $P(k)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics obtained using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when identifying the separation in r_{ij} .

Figure 6.9: Comparison of the actual degree distribution $P(k)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics with the averaging time $T_{av} = 5000$.

Finally, we proceed to the distribution of the node strength. The node strength s_i of the WSF network has a power-law distribution, likewise the distribution $P(S)$ of the normalized node strength S_i also follows this power-law with a difference only in the coefficient. The actual normalized node strength distribution $P(S)$ and that inferred using $S_i^{(e)}$ are compared in Fig. 6.10. Our method reproduces $P(S)$ satisfactorily for all the cases studied. Although there are nodes with small S_i that does not exist in the actual network, the extent is much less than what we observed in $P(k)$. Also, the underestimation of $P(S)$ in the intermediate regime for FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics is much weaker than its $P(k)$ counterpart. The relatively good performance of inferring $P(S)$ for the FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on WSF network is in contrast to the less than satisfactory results of comparing individual values of S_i for these cases in Chapter 5. This is because reconstructing global properties such as the node strength distribution is a less stringent requirement than inferring all the local information, and for the sole purpose of inferring global features our method could work for a wider range of scenarios. In Fig. 6.11 we see that using the criterion in Eq. (4.7) instead when finding the separation in the values of r_{ij} improves the slight underestimation of $P(S)$ in the regime of intermediate S similar to the case with $P(k)$. Moreover, increasing the averaging time T_{av} would reduce the density of nodes with very small values of $S_i^{(e)}$ that are incorrectly inferred.

Figure 6.10: Comparison of the actual node strength distribution $P(S)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) consensus dynamics, (b) Rössler dynamics, (c) FHN1 dynamics, and (d) FHN2 dynamics.

Figure 6.11: Comparison of the actual node strength distribution $P(S)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics obtained using the criterion specified in Eq. (4.7) instead when identifying the separation in r_{ij} .

Figure 6.12: Comparison of the actual node strength distribution $P(S)$ of the WSF network (circles) and the inferred distribution (triangles) using (a) FHN1 dynamics and (b) FHN2 dynamics with the averaging time $T_{av} = 5000$.

Chapter 7

Conclusion and Outlook

7.1 Summary

In this thesis, we have reviewed the background of the study of networks which is an increasingly important subject nowadays because of its ubiquitous presence in many different scientific disciplines. We have discussed the challenges in determining the crucial information of network connectivity and outlined various existing methods that reconstruct a network from its measured activity. These methods are impaired by a number of issues such as the presence of indirect connections, underdetermination of the problem, and the requirement of additional information other than the measured dynamics that is not readily available.

We have developed a novel method of network reconstruction that infers the connectivity of a network using only the nodal time series without needing additional information such as the response of the network to perturbations. Our method is based on a noise-induced relation between the network connectivity and the pseudoinverse of the dynamical covariance matrix \hat{C}^+ . By finding the separation in the ratios r_{ij} of the off-diagonal to

diagonal terms of \hat{C}^+ for each node i , we are able to identify the links in the network. Our method is not restricted to particular types of networks and is even applicable to weighted networks to infer the normalized coupling strength. We have shown that our method is exact assuming the consensus dynamics in the limit of long averaging time, but numerical results support that it can be applied to other nonlinear dynamics and coupling functions. Given a reasonable amount of noise and sufficiently large coupling strength or averaging time, our method works satisfactorily according to the overall sensitivity and specificity.

Reconstructing weighted networks is generally more challenging, especially for the WSF network which has large disparity of the coupling strength for some nodes. Nonetheless, our method is able to achieve good sensitivity and specificity for most of the cases and the unsatisfactory cases of the nonlinear FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on the WSF network can be improved by not using the exceptionally large differences when calculating the threshold for identifying a separation in r_{ij} or by lengthening the averaging time. For the reconstruction of normalized coupling strength G_{ij} , our method yields accurate information for all cases studied except for the WSF network with FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics. Results of the latter can be described by the generalization $G_{ij}^{(e)} = DG_{ij}$ with D less than but close to one. Furthermore, D becomes closer to one if the exceptionally large differences in r_{ij} are not included in setting up the threshold for identifying a separation or when a longer averaging time is used. Our method also provides accurate information for the normalized node strength again with exception only for FHN1 and FHN2 dynamics on the WSF network. The discrepancy is related to errors in inferring the degree of the nodes. Finally, our method successfully reproduces global features of the network such as the eigenvalue spectrum,

degree distribution and distributions of the normalized coupling strength and node strength.

We expect that our method should find application in real networks with bidirectional coupling as noise is pervasive in all kinds of real systems. An example would be networks of cultured cardiac cells [75] in which the gap junctions give bidirectional coupling. Applying our method to dynamical time series from such networks may yield insight on how the network connectivity changes as the culture matures and the relationship between connectivity and the synchronization of beating observed in these networks. On the other hand, there is also a number of factors that may limit the applicability of our method. These limitations will be discussed in the next section together with suggestions for possible future investigation.

7.2 Limitations of our method and suggestions for further investigation

A main limitation of our method is that it is only applicable to networks with bidirectional coupling. Many systems such as network of neurons have directional links and our method would not be applicable in these cases. In general, it is difficult to determine the direction of connections in a network, and this limitation applies to all symmetric metric including conditional correlation, partial correlation and mutual information. However, our method can be generalized to asymmetric couplings by introducing a temporal shift or lag τ in the covariance:

$$C_{ij}(\tau) \equiv \langle [x_i(t) - X(t)][x_j(t + \tau) - X(t + \tau)] \rangle. \quad (7.1)$$

Other lag-based measures such as Granger causality [76] have also been proposed [77, 78]. However, these approaches may perform poorer than correlation-based methods in identifying the underlying undirected network in some cases, for example, it has been found that they give very poor performance when applied to simulated fMRI time series [35]. We speculate that some combined approach of first using a symmetric metric to identify the connections and then applying a lag-based measure to determine the direction of each link may lead to improvement in performance, but in any case reconstructing a directed network is still largely an open question.

A fundamental limitation that is shared by virtually all methods of network reconstruction that utilizes the measured dynamics of the network is the requirement for a large amount of data. This usually manifests as the requirement for a sufficiently long time series. We have seen that for our method a certain minimum amount of coupling strength is required at a fixed averaging time for satisfactory reconstruction. Equivalently, that means our method requires a longer averaging time to uncover weaker connections. In some systems such as gene networks, it is difficult to obtain long time series due to experimental constraints, which may pose the problem of insufficient statistics for the reconstruction. There has been attempts at using compressive sensing to reduce the amount of data required for reconstruction [79], but it requires the additional assumption of sparseness of the network connectivity, which only applies to specific types of networks. Given the underdetermined nature of the problem, any method that can significantly lower the number of measurements required must constrain the degrees of freedom by postulating additional conditions that make it useful only under particular contexts.

Another limitation of our method is the requirement for a homogeneous Gaussian white noise. For some systems, there may be different types of

nodes and some of which may be inherently more noisy than others. For the case of an inhomogeneous Gaussian white noise, Eq. (3.2) becomes

$$\overline{\eta_i(t)\eta_j(t')} = \sigma_i\sigma_j\delta_{ij}\delta(t-t'). \quad (7.2)$$

In such a case, the derivation in Chapter 3 is not applicable as Eqs. (3.16) to (3.18) rely on a simplification that requires both the homogeneity of the noise amplitude and the orthogonality of the matrix \hat{P} . In addition to the issue of inhomogeneity, the derivation also requires white noise and for other types of noise we would have to evaluate a more complicated double integral in Eq. (3.19) instead of the current simple form that can be readily computed. As part of the future investigation, it would be especially interesting to study the more complex relationship between the network connectivity and the dynamical covariance for inhomogeneous noise or other types of noise such as colored noise.

Finally, our method requires the dynamics of all nodes in the network to be measured simultaneously as the computation of any element C_{ij}^+ of the pseudoinverse matrix requires the entire dynamical covariance matrix \hat{C} , and therefore the dynamics of all the nodes to be known. In fact, our results imply that if one would like to infer the connectivity between two nodes, information about the other nodes is also crucial, and the use of simple pairwise correlation would lead to errors. However, in actual experiments it is often not possible to measure all the nodes, and in such a case of partial or missing information, the computation of C_{ij}^+ would be impossible for any pair of i and j . To study and tackle this problem, suppose for a network of N nodes only a subnetwork \hat{S} consisting of the n nodes $\vec{s} \equiv (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n)$ can be measured, we define the elements of the $(n \times n)$ subnetwork dynamical

covariance matrix $\hat{C}_{\hat{S}}$ as

$$C_{\hat{S},ij} = \langle [x_i(t) - X_{\hat{S}}(t)][x_j(t) - X_{\hat{S}}(t)] \rangle_T \quad (7.3)$$

where $X_{\hat{S}}(t) \equiv (1/n) \sum_{i=1}^n x_{s_i}(t)$ is the average activity of the subnetwork at time t . The pseudoinverse $\hat{C}_{\hat{S}}^+$ of the matrix $\hat{C}_{\hat{S}}$ can then be calculated using only the time series of the nodes that can be measured. In the trivial case of $n = N$ where the information is complete, it reduces to what we have considered throughout this thesis and we expect $r_{\hat{S},ij} \equiv C_{\hat{S},ij}/C_{\hat{S},ii}$ can give us accurate information about the network connectivity. Therefore the question is whether $r_{\hat{S},ij}$ can still convey the connectivity information of the subnetwork when $n < N$. More specifically, we would like to ascertain the conditions under which $r_{\hat{S},ij}$ can be used to reconstruct the subnetwork with reasonable accuracy. Preliminary results on random network with consensus dynamics show that the separation in the values of $r_{\hat{S},ij}$ still exist even when the states of a substantial number of nodes are unknown, and the separation reliably predicts the links in the subnetwork. It would be especially interesting to further study the effect of partial information in networks with non-trivial properties. For example, scale-free networks contain hubs with high degree that serve important function in the network. Thus the activity of hubs may also be important in conveying information about the connectivity of other parts of the network. This can be tested by comparing the reconstruction of the subnetwork using $r_{\hat{S},ij}$ in the following two cases: (i) the information of a number of random nodes is unknown and (ii) the information of the same number of hubs is unknown. If case (ii) results in significantly more errors than case (i), it would indicate that the hubs are more important for network reconstruction. Furthermore, we would like to be able to predict the reconstruction performance using only the available

information, so another possible direction of research would be to determine whether the size of separation in $r_{\hat{S},ij}$ as used in $\delta(i)$ is still a good indicator of the reconstruction accuracy in the more general context accounting for partial information.

Appendix A

Numerical Methods used in Solving Stochastic Differential Equations (SDE)

A.1 The Euler-Maruyama method

The Euler-Maruyama method [64] is an analogue of the Euler method that is used to solve stochastic differential equations. More specifically, consider the stochastic differential equation (SDE) initial value problem:

$$\begin{aligned} dx(t) &= A(t, x)dt + B(t, x)dW_t \\ x(0) &= x_0 \end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

where W_t is the Wiener process which is the standard Brownian motion. The Euler-Maruyama method approximates the values of x at a series of time points $t_0 < t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_n$ as $(\omega_0, \omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n)$ by the following

iterative process:

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_0 &= x_0 \\ \omega_{i+1} &= \omega_i + A(t_i, \omega_i)\Delta t_{i+1} + B(t_i, \omega_i)\Delta W_{i+1}\end{aligned}\tag{A.2}$$

where $\Delta t_{i+1} \equiv t_{i+1} - t_i$ and $\Delta W_{i+1} \equiv W(t_{i+1}) - W(t_i)$. For our case $B(t_i, \omega_i) = \sigma$ is a constant noise amplitude. The Brownian motion ΔW_i is then modeled by

$$\Delta W_i = \zeta_i \sqrt{\Delta t_i}\tag{A.3}$$

where ζ_i is a random number chosen from a Gaussian distribution with mean 0 and standard deviation 1. The accuracy of the Euler-Maruyama method is given by its strong order of convergence 1/2 and weak order of convergence 1. The former means that an individual realization converges as $\Delta t^{1/2}$ while the latter indicates that the probability distribution of the solution converges as Δt .

A.2 The Weak Order 2 Runge-Kutta (RKW2) method

As its name suggests, the Weak Order 2 Runge-Kutta (RKW2) method [64] has weak order of convergence 2, which is superior to the Euler-Maruyama method with only weak order 1. The RKW2 method is defined as the fol-

lowing iterative scheme:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \omega_0 &= x_0 \\
 \omega_{i+1} &= \omega_i + \frac{1}{2}[A(u) + A(\omega_i)]\Delta t_i \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{4}[B(u_+) + B(u_-) + 2B(\omega_i)]\Delta W_i \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{4}[B(u_+) - B(u_-)](\Delta W_i^2 - \Delta t_i)/\sqrt{\Delta t_i} \quad (\text{A.4})
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= \omega_i + A\Delta t_i + B\Delta W_i \\
 u_+ &= \omega_i + A\Delta t_i + B\sqrt{\Delta t_i} \\
 u_- &= \omega_i + A\Delta t_i - B\sqrt{\Delta t_i} .
 \end{aligned}$$

For our case $B(\omega) = \sigma$ is a constant, so Eq. (A.4) can be simplified to

$$\omega_{i+1} = \omega_i + \frac{1}{2}[A(u) + A(\omega_i)]\Delta t_i + \sigma\Delta W_i . \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Again the Brownian motion ΔW_i is modeled by Eq. (A.3).

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